

APPENDIX 1A: Baseline Study

In Recto-spect: Investigating the Present Landscape Character and Public Perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip

Memoryscapes in Recto-spection:
Visualizing Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoryscapes
through immersive mobile technologies and digital heritage interpretation

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**In Recto-spect: Investigating the Present Landscape Character
and Public Perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip**

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Abstract

The Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip in Manila, Philippines, holds a significant place in the city's history as a vibrant commercial and cinematic district. However, over time, the area has suffered from degradation and neglect, leading to the loss of its historical character and fostering of negative place character. To address these challenges and promote the revival of the strip, a proposed solution involves the investigation of its present landscape character and the preference of the public in the potential incorporation of landscape elements in the study area.

This study explores the landscape character and preferences of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip in Manila, Philippines. The analysis reveals that Rizal Avenue, Recto Avenue, and Carriedo Street hold historical significance as they are associated with landmarks and prominent figures in Philippine history. These streets also serve as vibrant commercial centers, offering a diverse range of shops and bustling street markets. Additionally, they function as key transportation hubs, facilitating connectivity and accessibility within the city through the presence of Light Rail Transit stations. The cultural diversity and vibrant street life along these streets further contribute to the urban atmosphere.

Furthermore, the study highlights the priorities expressed by respondents for improving the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Safety emerges as a crucial concern, with a consensus on the need for CCTV Units, lamp posts, and police outposts. Additionally, the inclusion of landscape elements such as trash receptacles, softscape materials, public restrooms, wayfinding signage, and information boards addresses the community's desire for cleanliness, aesthetics, organization, and convenience. The emphasis on accessibility through PWD ramps, pedestrian lanes, transportation bays, and bike lanes reflects a commitment to inclusivity and sustainable transportation options.

These findings have significant implications for urban planners and decision-makers involved in the enhancement of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. By incorporating the identified preferences, they can create a safer, more accessible, and user-friendly urban environment that respects the historical and cultural significance of these streets. Ultimately, this research contributes to the understanding and preservation of Manila's urban landscape, promoting the quality of life for its residents and visitors.

Keywords: *Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, Landscape Perception Survey, Evidence Synthesis Procedure, Landscape Preference and Improvement, Public Perception, Image of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, Place Character*

Introduction

Manila, the capital city of the Philippines, was known as “the Pearl of the Orient” in its former glory, citing its strategic location for trade and commerce due to its centrality in Southeast Asia. Throughout time, the city’s commercial center has shifted from Intramuros to the city’s historic downtown on the opposite shore of the Pasig River from the mid-1500s to the late 1800s (Bondoc, Labayen, & Tutor, 2004; MTCDP, 2020; Gomez, 2022). After World War II, the core of trading activities has shifted to Sta. Cruz, Manila, where Avenida (presently called Rizal Avenue) was the focus of this district. It is an arterial road spanning from Carriedo Street in the south to the Bonifacio Monument in the north. Perpendicular to this thoroughfare, Claro M. Recto Avenue is also part of Manila’s old Downtown, formerly known as Calle Azcarraga during the Spanish Rule (Bondoc, Labayen, & Tutor, 2004).

The Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip was Manila’s center of commerce in the twentieth century, famously known for its numerous commercial and trade establishments, bazaars, and movie houses. (Bondoc, Labayen, & Tutor, 2004; Lico, 2020; Diala, 2022). In 1979, the declaration of Martial Law and the construction of the Light Rail Transit System (LRT) and other thoroughfares in the area has significantly contributed to the degradation and decay of the strip’s local character – which has led to the proliferation of urban crimes and the negative associations attached to the place’s character (Bondoc, Labayen, & Tutor, 2004; MTCDP, 2020). Some of the undesirable effects that was a consequence of this rapid development was air pollution with fumes from vehicular traffic being trapped underneath the rail structure, proliferation of theft, illegal drugs, and prostitution (Bondoc, Labayen, & Tutor, 2004; Gomez, 2022).

At the turn of the new millennium, urban renewal programs have been implemented by the Local Government Unit of Manila through the “Buhayin ang Maynila” program to beautify Manila’s urban spaces and to remove undesirable connotations of the public with the city. The program sought to improve decaying public infrastructure, facilities, and open spaces throughout the city, including Avenida, which was dubbed as a virtual ghost town by Jose “Lito” Atienza, the city’s former mayor. Aside from this program’s notable projects, which include the redevelopment of Manila Baywalk and the creation of plazas such as the Rajah Sulayman Park, the revitalization of Manila’s old Downtown area was carried out, which includes the pedestrianization of Carriedo and its conversion as a pedestrian shopping strip which had brought economic benefits and vitality to the area (Gomez, 2022). Many pre-war buildings, particularly those that follow the Art Deco style, were restored, and the streets were adorned with vibrant Machuca tiles (Enrique, 2006 in Gomez, 2022). This project was met with public praise as it primarily benefitted pedestrians and the city’s informal economy. However, the strip was

reverted to its original state favoring public and private vehicles over pedestrians (Bondoc, Labayen, & Tutor, 2004; MTCDP, 2020; Gomez, 2022).

At present, the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip is only known as a major thoroughfare connecting numerous districts in Manila, with its past as a major commercial and entertainment hub forgotten in the minds of many (MTCDP, 2020; Gomez, 2022). For the interest of promoting the historical significance of the place and its contributions to Manila's cinematic and commercial history, there is a need for a holistic revival of these historical places which takes the narratives and ideologies that has shaped the place into account (Acharron, 2013; Biascan, 2019; Cabrera, 2019; Trias, 2022).

Conducting an examination of the present landscape character of the study site is imperative to gain insights into the public's perception of the site in its current state. By systematically assessing the existing condition and aesthetic qualities of the study area, researchers can discern how the public perceives and interacts with the space. This evaluation encompasses various aspects, including visual appeal, functionality, accessibility, and overall ambiance. Furthermore, such an assessment aims to elucidate the preferences of the public regarding the incorporation of landscape elements as potential means of enhancing the quality and usability of the spaces within the study site. By understanding the public's desires and expectations regarding the integration of landscape elements, researchers can gain valuable information on the desired improvements, amenities, and design features that would be most beneficial to the users. This knowledge contributes to evidence-based decision-making in urban design and landscape architecture, ensuring that future interventions align with the preferences and aspirations of the public. Additionally, exploring the public's preferences provides an opportunity to gauge the perceived value and potential impact of incorporating landscape elements within the study site. It allows for an examination of how such interventions may influence the public's perception of the site, its attractiveness, and its overall experiential qualities. Ultimately, by undertaking an examination of the present landscape character and determining the public's preferences for incorporating landscape elements, researchers can inform design strategies and interventions that align with the desires and needs of the users, thus fostering a more inclusive and user-centered approach to urban planning and design.

Statement of the Problem

How does the public perceive the past and present place character of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip based on literature and on their subjective experiences?

Goal of the Study

The study aims to investigate the landscape character of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo strip through the Evidence Synthesis Procedure and the Landscape Perception and Preference Survey. It also seeks to conduct a thematic analysis of the place character of the study site based on the data collected from the survey.

Significance of The Study

The significance of the study lies in its contribution to the understanding and improvement of the study site's landscape character and public perception. By examining the present landscape character, the study provides valuable insights into how the public perceives the site in its current state. This understanding can inform future design and planning decisions to enhance the quality, functionality, and attractiveness of the space. Moreover, by determining the preferences of the public regarding the incorporation of landscape elements, the study offers guidance on potential improvements and interventions that would be most beneficial to the users. This knowledge aids in evidence-based decision-making and ensures that design strategies align with the desires and aspirations of the public.

The study's findings have broader implications for urban design and landscape architecture practices. They contribute to the body of knowledge in these fields by providing empirical data on the public's perception and preferences related to the study site. This information can guide professionals and policymakers in creating more inclusive and user-centered urban spaces. Additionally, the study promotes the importance of public engagement and participatory approaches in urban planning and design processes. By considering the perspectives and desires of the public, the study advocates for a collaborative decision-making process that values community input and fosters a sense of ownership and connection to the study site.

Methods

Description of Data Sources

This subsection provides an overview of the data sourced used in this research. These sources include secondary data sources, such as books, scholarly journals, theses, online websites, and government records. In addition, primary data collection instruments, such as the Landscape Perception Survey, and the Virtual Memoryscapes Tool Kit, were also used in the data gathering procedure.

A. Landscape Perception Survey

A Landscape Perception Survey was employed to understand the research problem and identify the perceptions of the respondents with regards to the study site. The survey included the use of open-ended questions, a scale rating, and a visual perception rating. The target population of the survey included Manila residents and non-residents who were familiar with the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip who were 15 years old or older during the conduct of the study.

B. Scholarly Journals

The current study included local and international scholarly journals related to the study site, histo-cultural landscapes, heritage-led immersive experiences, participatory planning, and immersive technologies. These resources laid the framework for the methodology and the creation of the visual memoryscape. These references were listed and cited in *Chapter 3: Review of Related Literature*, *Chapter 5: Research Methodology*, and *Bibliography*.

C. Theses

The current study also made use of undergraduate and graduate theses from the university and college library, and from numerous international and local sources. These included Trias's 2022 and Weir's 2021 studies on histo-cultural landscapes in Manila and memoryscapes in the Philippines. They were used as references in the conception of frameworks, methodologies, concepts, theories, and strategies which were used to obtain the objectives and goals of the present study.

D. Published Books

Local and international published books were also examined in investigating the necessary concepts, frameworks and procedures used in the study. This included Gerard Lico's (2021) book entitled "*Pa(NG)labas: Architecture + Cinema, Projections of Filipino Space in Film*", which was relevant to the present study as it discussed the history of cinematic districts in the Philippines, which includes the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Moverover, this type of literature primarily tackled topics related to current study ranging from

landscape studies, memoryscapes, cultural heritage, immersive technologies, and participatory planning.

E. Government Records

A number of statistical records, laws and legislations, and archives were also examined to determine the present conditions and inventory of the site. These included the Manila Tourism and Cultural Development Plan 2020 – 2025 from the Local Government of Manila.

F. Online Sources

In order to obtain a comprehensive background and framework needed for the present thesis, online resources were used as the primary resources for related literature and information. These included websites, blog posts, articles, videos, and documentaries about the study site and heritage-led immersive technologies. Online articles from Google Scholar were also used for the Evidence Synthesis Procedure and Landscape Perception Survey.

Landscape Perception and Preference Survey

The *Landscape Perception and Preference Survey* was carried out to obtain specific perspectives and sentiments from the target population that contributed data from the research design. This survey also contains appropriate questions and photos to uncover a representative of the landscape character of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. This survey based on Edrienne Mae Trias's (2022) study entitled "*Capturing the Dynamic Character of the Philippine Peri-urban Landscape: A Landscape Character Approach for the Region of Cavite*" and "*Lens of the Present Pasts: Reimagining a Histo-Cultural Trail for Tondo, Manila through a Hybridized Landscape-based Walking Approach*" was used to investigate the public's current perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip at present. It consisted of three types of questions, particularly (1) open-ended questions, (2) Stapel Scale Ratings, and (3) Visual Perception Rating, and Assessment of Landscape Preference / Improvement.

The survey form targeted the working-age and elderly population within and outside the city of Manila separated with age groups ranging from 15 – 64 years old, and 65 years old and above. The survey was written in both English and Filipino and was delivered in both digital

and print format. Further, the survey was not limited to locals within the study site but opened to all Manila residents to intensively investigate the image of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. The respondents were selected through purposive sampling with a 95% confidence level and 7% margin of error, and a population size of 179,508 which was obtained from the latest number of visitors during peak season within the study site (Saraom 2023). which resulted in a sample size of 196. The computation for the sample size may be found below.

$$n = \frac{NZ^2_{\alpha}p(1-p)}{Z^2_{\alpha}p(1-p) + (N-1)\epsilon^2}$$

Where n is the sample size, N is the population size, α is the significance level, p is the population proportion, which is usually 0.5 to achieve the maximum possible sample size, and Z is the Z-score in the standard normal distribution.

Created in Google Forms, the survey questionnaire comprises four distinct sections, encompassing various aspects related to the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. The first section, known as the **Demographic Assessment**, aims to collect fundamental information about the respondents' demographic profiles. It includes basic questions regarding their background and characteristics. The second section of the questionnaire consists of **Open-ended Questions** that prompt respondents to provide their individual perspectives on the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. These questions encourage participants to express their thoughts, opinions, and perceptions regarding the aforementioned area. The third section employs the **Stapel Scale Rating** methodology, which entails a series of associators for respondents to rate. These associators are designed to measure the participants' personal understanding and perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. The fourth and final section involves the **Visual Perception Rating and the Assessment of Landscape Preference/Improvement**. This section aims to evaluate the extent to which selected images align with the respondents' current experiences and perceptions of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Additionally, it seeks to assess which specific landscape elements could be incorporated to enhance the open spaces and streetscapes of the aforementioned area.

Evidence Synthesis Procedure

The *evidence synthesis procedure* was used to determine the top 35 *associators* that people associate with the image of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip for the landscape perception survey. It is a systematic process of extracting landscape data from a set of online references, which involves the use of search engines, protocols, and datasets. This procedure was adapted from Cathe Desiree Nadal (2021) and Edrienne Mae Trias's (2022) studies entitled "*Capturing the Dynamic Character of the Philippine Peri-urban Landscape: A Landscape Character Approach for the Region of Cavite*" and "*Lens of the Present Past: Reimagining a Historical Cultural Trail for Tondo, Manila through a Hybridized Landscape-based Walking Approach*", respectively.

In particular, it used the following steps and frameworks based and adapted from "*The Evidence Synthesis Procedure for Landscape Data Extraction as applied in Cavite's Peri-urban Landscape Phenomena Mapping: Checklists, Tools, Meta-analysis*" (Nadal, 2021), and "*The Tondo Picture: Identifying Terminologies and Concepts that People Associate with Tondo, Manila, Through and Evidence Synthesis Procedure*" (Trias, 2022).

A. Determining a search question

In Nadal's (2021) study, a data set was utilized, which involved the utilization of a data extraction form. This form was employed to document the search question, which inquired about the words associated with Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, located in Manila, concerning landscapes, history or culture, and memories or experiences. The purpose of this question was to analyze and quantify the various terminologies, titles, concepts, and descriptors that individuals connect with the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip in relation to the aforementioned factors.

B. Developing a search protocol

The data extraction form implemented a search protocol to establish the guidelines for identifying associated words. In this study, the search protocol encompassed two key components: (1) the utilization of Google Scholar as the primary search engine and (2) the application of a search string syntax based on the principles of Boolean search. Boolean search is a sophisticated and systematic approach to online searching that enables users to incorporate specific characters, words, or operators, such as "and," "or,"

"not," parentheses (), and asterisk *, to refine and delineate the search results (TalentLyft, 2022 in Trias, 2022).

C. Using the search strategy and applying the search protocol

The implemented search protocol served as a means to investigate potential answers pertaining to the specified search question. The procedure entailed inputting the newly developed search string protocol into the search bar of Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.com>) and initiating the search by pressing the enter or search button. In the context of this study, the utilized search string syntax was as follows:

*(Avenida OR Recto OR Carriedo OR Dulumbayan OR Azcarraga OR Rizal
Avenue AND Manila) AND (histor* OR cultur*) AND (memor* OR
experienc*) AND land**

D. Screening the results through inclusion and exclusion criteria

Once the search protocol was initiated, a considerable number of articles related to the search question were retrieved, yielding a substantial volume of potential sources. In order to narrow down the selection and identify the most relevant articles, specific inclusion and exclusion criteria were established. These criteria were developed based on insights from Trias (2022) and Nadal (2021) and are outlined as follows:

▪ INCLUSIONS Criteria

- Accessible books, PDFs and HTMLs on Google Scholar
- Journal articles, biographies, literature, and reviews available on Google Scholar
- Search Results within the first 36 pages of Google Scholar
- Available local and international articles mentioning Avenida, Recto, or Carriedo

▪ EXCLUSIONS Criteria

- Files/articles with required payment or inaccessible
- Unsearchable files/articles
- Results with no direct link to the file/article

- Files/articles that do not mention Avenida, Recto, or Carriedo as places in Manila, Philippines
- Repeating/similar results/articles
- Search results from Page 36 and beyond

E. Extracting the evidence or associators

The obtained data results underwent a rigorous screening process based on the established criteria. The data results that fulfilled the Inclusion Criteria were subjected to a digital search aimed at extracting relevant evidence or associators, specifically words associated with Recto, Carriedo, and/or Avenida in Manila. Furthermore, attention was given to words or phrases found within the same sentence or in close proximity to the study site. These words, which depicted the landscape, history, memory, culture, or experience of Recto, Carriedo, and/or Avenida in Manila, were extracted and considered as *associators* in the study (Trias, 2022).

F. Synthesizing the results into datasets

Following the screening of each eligible search result, the references that were utilized and the associators that were extracted were integrated into datasets. These datasets were structured in the form of organized tables and tallies to facilitate data analysis. The references used in the study were compiled into a table, encompassing essential details such as the author(s), title, country of origin, year of publication, type of data, link, and assigned item code. This comprehensive table allowed for easy reference and traceability of the sources employed. On the other hand, the extracted associators, which consisted of the words or phrases associated with Recto, Carriedo, and/or Avenida in Manila, were tabulated alongside their respective tally counts and corresponding references. This tabulated information served to provide a clear representation of the frequency of occurrence for each associator and indicated the item codes associated with their extraction. The synthesis of these references and associators into systematized tables and tallies enabled a systematic analysis of the data, facilitating the interpretation and presentation of the findings (Trias, 2022)

Results and Discussion

Landscape Perception and Preference Survey Results and Findings

The following section describes the findings from the Landscape Perception and Preference Survey. The aim of this tool is to establish the current landscape character of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip based on a series of open-ended questions, Stapel scale ratings, visual perception ratings, and assessment of landscape preferences and improvement. The data gathered from this instrument gives a glimpse into the needs of the community and the users of the study site, and which areas must be prioritized in the creation of redevelopments within the area. Moreover, the results of this survey provide insights to the participants of the co-design workshop session in the creation of schematic designs for selected areas in the study site.

The online version of the survey included Filipino and English translations, whereas the physical version of the survey included questions in Filipino. A total of 200 participants answered the survey questionnaire, despite having a target number of 196 based on the computed sample size. As non-random sampling was employed throughout the conduct of this survey, the results of the survey were only applicable to the respondents, and not necessarily to the whole population within the study site, who are either pedestrians, motorists, commuters, or community members. The results still provide reasonable framework for the conduct of the study, in spite of the challenges posed in the usage of non-probability sampling. The following results are mostly descriptive statistics, and no inferential tests were used for its analysis. The data was processed using Microsoft Excel 2021, Google Forms, and Adobe Illustrator for visualization purposes.

A. Demographic Assessment

The following figures and tables describe the demographics of people who consented to answer the survey questionnaire and be part of the study. Based on the figure below, 112 of respondents, which constitutes 56% of respondents identify as female, while 42.5% or 85 people identified as male. The remaining 1.5% or 3 people prefer not to disclose their sex assigned at birth.

Figure 1. Gender Demographics

Consequently, the majority of the respondents belong to the 18 – 24 age bracket, with 43% of respondents, or 86 people filling in that category. The age bracket with the lower respondent turnout includes the Above 65 years old group, which only constituted 6% of the respondents, or 12 people. Along with this, 54% of respondents, or 108 people, identified as students; 40 people or 20% of respondents are employed for wages; while 10% of respondents or 20 people are self-employed. The remaining 16% or 32 respondents are employed as members of a non-governmental organization, design professionals, business leaders or intermediaries within the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Whereas the remaining of them identified as homemakers, unemployed, unable to work, or retired.

Figure 2. Age Brackets

Figure 3. Employment Status

Two groups were identified based on the place of residence within the respondents. 54 people, or 27% of respondents resided outside Manila, which includes cities from Metro Manila and its surrounding provinces like Cavite, Laguna, Rizal, and Bulacan. In contrast, the remaining 146 people, or 73% of respondents resided within Manila, with 70 people, or roughly 48% of this population resided in either Sta. Cruz or Quiapo, Manila.

Figure 4. Place of Residence

Lastly, four groups were formed based on the length of residency within or outside of the city of Manila. 21% of respondents, or 42 people cited that they lived within Manila for more than 10 years, 8%, or 15 people mentioned that they lived within the city from 5 to 10 years, while 6.5% or 12 respondents stated that they only lived in Manila for less than 5 years. The remaining 64.5% of respondents, or 131 people, answered that this question was not applicable to their place of residence.

Figure 5. Length of Residence in Manila

B. Open-Ended Questions

The following set of results are related to the answers of the survey responses to open-ended questions about heritage and the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Respondents are

The responses from the participants regarding the landscape characteristics of Rizal Avenue provide valuable insights into the key elements that shape its physical environment and overall ambiance. The mentions of the *LRT* highlight the significance of this transportation infrastructure in defining the avenue's landscape character, as it serves as a major mode of transportation for commuters and contributes to the movement and vibrancy of the area. The descriptions of Rizal Avenue as "*busy*," "*congested*," and "*populous*" indicate the dynamic and bustling nature of the streetscape. These characteristics suggest a high volume of pedestrian and vehicular activity, creating a lively and energetic atmosphere within the area. However, it is worth noting that the perception of congestion and busyness may also raise concerns about traffic flow and pedestrian movement, underscoring the need for effective urban planning and management strategies to ensure efficient mobility and pedestrian safety.

The mention of *dilapidated sidewalks* draws attention to the physical condition of pedestrian walkways along Rizal Avenue. This observation suggests that the state of infrastructure, specifically sidewalks, may require attention and improvement to enhance the overall pedestrian experience and ensure accessibility for all users. This finding highlights the importance of investing in the maintenance and upgrade of pedestrian facilities to create a more pedestrian-friendly environment. The presence of commercial establishments and churches within the landscape character of Rizal Avenue reflects its role as a hub for economic activities and religious institutions. These elements contribute to the avenue's social and cultural significance, attracting people for various purposes such as shopping, dining, and worship. The diverse mix of commercial and religious spaces adds to the vibrant and multifaceted nature of Rizal Avenue.

It is noteworthy that only a few respondents mentioned *the lack of planting and adequate pedestrian facilities within the area*. This observation suggests that there may be an opportunity for improvement in terms of greening initiatives and creating more pedestrian-oriented spaces. Integrating greenery, such as trees and landscaping, can contribute to a more visually appealing and environmentally friendly streetscape. Additionally, providing well-designed and accessible pedestrian facilities, including sidewalks, crosswalks, and amenities, can enhance walkability and promote active transportation along Rizal Avenue.

association with the street. This association highlights the cultural and religious importance of the Quiapo Church, positioning it as a central landmark that shapes the identity of Carriedo Street. The mention of the *LRT Station* signifies the transportation significance of Carriedo Street, highlighting the presence of a major transit hub within the area. This association emphasizes the role of Carriedo Street as a transportation artery, facilitating the movement of commuters and connecting them to various parts of the city. *Carriedo Plaza and Fountain* also feature prominently in the responses, indicating their significance as focal points within the street. These elements contribute to the overall character and ambiance of Carriedo Street, serving as gathering spaces and landmarks for residents and visitors alike. The mention of Optical Shops points to the prevalence of these establishments along Carriedo Street. This association suggests that the street is recognized as a hub for optical services, offering a range of eyewear options and related services to cater to the needs of the community.

The reference to Muslim communities highlights the diversity and cultural richness present within the area. This association suggests the presence of *Muslim residents and businesses*, contributing to the multicultural fabric of Carriedo Street. The mention of the informal economy or street vendors reflects the existence of a vibrant street market along Carriedo Street. This association underscores the economic activities and livelihoods supported by the street, providing opportunities for small-scale entrepreneurs and contributing to the local economy. The presence of old buildings alludes to the historical significance of Carriedo Street, indicating the existence of architectural heritage within the area. This association contributes to the street's sense of place and adds to its cultural and historical appeal. Lastly, the reference to crowded rush hours suggests the dynamic and bustling nature of Carriedo Street during peak periods. This observation indicates the high volume of pedestrian and vehicular traffic experienced along the street, reflecting its role as a major thoroughfare within the city.

Figure 12. Word Cloud depicting words that people associate with the term Heritage

The responses provided by the participants shed light on the associations and perceptions related to the concept of heritage. The most frequently mentioned words—culture, legacy, and history—underscore the intrinsic connection between heritage and broader cultural contexts. These terms reflect an understanding that heritage encompasses the collective knowledge, values, and practices passed down from previous generations, shaping the identity and sense of belonging of a community. In addition to the abstract concepts of culture, legacy, and history, participants also referenced more tangible objects associated with heritage. Monuments, antique objects, money, landmarks, and heirlooms were among the responses. These objects serve as physical manifestations of heritage, representing the material and artistic expressions of a particular era or culture. They act as touchstones for memory and serve as visual reminders of the past, embodying the significance and value of heritage. The common themes that emerge from the responses include notions of the past, inheritance, riches, traditions, culture, ancient customs, and wisdom. These terms reflect an appreciation for the historical depth and accumulated wisdom embedded within heritage. They highlight the importance of acknowledging and preserving traditional practices, customs, and knowledge systems as valuable sources of cultural identity and societal development.

The word cloud generated from the responses reflects the multifaceted nature of heritage. It encompasses both tangible and intangible aspects, ranging from physical objects and monuments to intangible traditions, customs, and wisdom. The association of heritage with culture, legacy, and history suggests an understanding of heritage as a dynamic and evolving concept that encompasses the collective experiences and expressions of a community. Understanding the significance of these terms and associations is crucial for heritage conservation and management. It emphasizes the need to preserve and transmit cultural practices, artifacts, and knowledge to future generations. By recognizing the value of heritage and its role in shaping identity and fostering a sense of continuity, communities and policymakers can implement strategies to safeguard and promote heritage as a valuable resource for social cohesion, education, and sustainable development.

C. Stapel Scale Rating

This part of the study aims to determine the ranking between 35 associators or terms that the respondents will rate according to their personal understanding and perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip from -3 to $+3$ with the former being an item which they does not highly match their personal experiences of the study site, while the latter pertaining to terms that highly matches their personal perception and experiences of the study site..

This part of the study used the median as the measure of central tendency for the data analysis. As the Stapel scale is generally treated as an ordinal scale, emphasizing the relative positioning or rank order of the ratings rather than their precise numerical distances, the median is particularly appropriate as it considers the order of the ratings and provides a meaningful representation of the central tendency. The mean was not used as a measure for this section as it can be influenced by outliers, and the scale cannot be considered as numerical values. Moreover, the median does not rely on any assumptions about the underlying distribution of the data. It is versatile and robust, applicable to various data distributions without requiring them to follow a specific pattern. The interpretability of the median further strengthens its appeal, as it represents the value that divides the data into two equal halves. The formula for the median is as follows:

$$\text{Median} = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} X_{\left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)}, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{X_{\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)} + X_{\left(\frac{n}{2}+1\right)}}{2}, & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{array} \right\}$$

Figure 13. Formula for Median

Conversely, the inter-quartile range was also used as a measure of dispersion, or its ability to capture the spread or variability of the ratings while being resistant to extreme values. By dividing the data into four equal parts, it is in line with the ordinal nature of the Stapel Scale. By calculating the IQR in this context, the dispersion of ratings in the middle two quartiles are essential in understanding the central tendency and variability of ordinal scales. The formula for the IQR is as follows.

$$\text{IQR} = 3\text{rd quartile} - 1\text{st quartile}$$

Figure 14. Formula for Interquartile Range

1. *How close do you associate the following terms to your 'current' perception/opinion of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip? Rate from -3 (far from your perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip) to 0 (neutral) to +3 (close to your perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.)*

#	ASSOCIATOR	MEDIAN	Q1	Q3	IQR
1	Shopping/Commercial District (<i>Pamilihan, sentro ng komersyo</i>)	3	2	3	1
2	Major thoroughfare and Mass Transit (<i>Pangunahing daanan</i>)	3	2	3	1
3	Busy pedestrian and motorist activities (<i>Nagsisiksikang mga komyuter at motorista</i>)	3	2	3	1
4	Filthy, dark, narrow alleyways (<i>Mga madilim, madumi, at masisikip na mga eskinita</i>)	3	2	3	1
5	Congested, overcrowded, populous (<i>Siksikan/Maraming tao</i>)	3	2	3	1
8	Informal Economy (Street vendors, hawking); <i>Impormal na Ekonomiya (Mga nagtitinda sa kalye, hawking)</i>	3	2	3	1
9	Petty Crimes, Violence and Illegal Activities (Pickpocketing, Gambling, Drug trafficking and Prostitution); <i>Mga Maliit na Krimen, Karahasan at Illegal na Aktibidad (Panunukot, Pagsusugal, Pagtutulak ng droga at Prostitusyon)</i>	3	2	3	1
10	Light Rail Transit (<i>LRT Lines 1 and 2</i>)	3	3	3	0
11	Noisy, shabby, unclean, and polluted (<i>Maingay, magulo, at marumi</i>)	3	2	3	1
15	Affordable goods and emporiums, retail, wholesale items (<i>Abot-kayang mga produkto at emporium, tingian, pakyawan na mga paninda</i>)	3	2	3	1
20	Fiesta, Popular Devotions and Traditions (<i>Mga pagdiriwang, popular na debosyon, at tradisyon</i>)	3	1	3	2
21	University Belt	3	2	3	1
23	Poverty, Slums, Informal Settlements, Beggars, Street Children (<i>Kahirapan, Barong-barong, Mga pulubi, Mga Batang Lansangan</i>)	3	2	3	1
24	Fake Documents/Counterfeit Items (<i>Mga pekeng dokumento at paninda</i>)	3	2	3	1

Memoryscapes in Recto-spection:
Visualizing Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoryscapes
through immersive mobile technologies and digital heritage interpretation

27	Electronic goods, printing press, furniture shops, shoe marts, restaurants (<i>Mga elektronikong kalakal, palimbagan, mga tindahan ng muwebles, mga tindahan ng sapatos, mga kainan</i>)	3	2	3	1
31	Jeepneys	3	3	3	0
33	Plazas (<i>Plaza Miranda, Plaza Carriedo, Plaza Sta. Cruz</i>)	3	2	3	1
14	Poor traffic conditions (<i>Hindi magandang kondisyon ng trapiko</i>)	2.5	2	3	1
6	Sociohistorical: Sites of important people and events (<i>Mga lugar kung saan naganap ang mahahalagang pangyayari at mga tao</i>)	2	0	2	2
7	Downtown Area / Red light district	2	0.75	3	2.25
13	Urban decay, ill-planned, Disorderly, Deteriorated, Urban Blight (<i>Hindi maayos na pag-paplano ng mga lugar, magulo, pagkabulok ng lugar</i>)	2	1	3	2
19	Church and Religious Sites and Orders, Christian and Muslim Communities (<i>Mga Simbahan, Mga Pamayanang Kristiyano at Muslim</i>)	2	1	3	2
25	Economic center after Escolta (<i>Sentro ng komersyo pagkatapos ng Escolta</i>)	2	0	3	3
26	Sociopolitical Organizations and Movements, Rallies and Demonstrations (<i>Mga organisasyong at kilusang sosyopulitikal</i>)	2	0	2.5	2.5
29	Pasig River and Estuary (<i>Ilog Pasig at mga Estero</i>)	2	0	3	3
32	Environmental and physical degradation (<i>Pagkasira ng kapaligiran at pisikal na katangian ng lugar</i>)	2	2	3	1
34	Buildings and Facilities Designed by Prominent Architects (<i>Mga gusali at pasilidad na dinisensyo ng mga tanyag na arkitekto</i>)	2	0	3	3
35	Protection of illegal vending (<i>Lagay, proteksyon ng ilegal na pagbebenta/paghahanap-buhay</i>)	2	0	3	3

12	Movie houses / theatres, cultural arts, and vaudevilles (<i>Mga sinehan, sining pangkultura, at teatro/tanghalan</i>)	1	-1	2	3
17	Renamed Streets ex. Calle Iris, Calle Azcarraga, Calle Dulumbayan, Calle Salcedo (<i>Mga pinalitang pangalan ng mga kalye</i>)	1	-1	2	3
22	Tranvia and Horse-drawn Carriages (<i>Tranvia at mga Kalesa</i>)	1	-1.3	2	3.25
28	Marcos Era-projects, Martial law, First Quarter Storm (<i>Proyekto noong panahon ni Marcos, Sr., Batas Militar, Sigwa ng Unang Sangkapat</i>)	1	0	2	2
16	Battle of Manila, World War II (<i>Labanan sa Maynila, Ikalawang Digmaang Pandaigdig</i>)	0	-1	2	3
18	Japanese Bazaar, Japanese settlements	0	-2	1	3
30	Little Tokyo/Ginza of Manila	0	-2	2	4

Table 1. Terms derived from the Evidence Synthesis Procedure

The majority of the items under this section garnered a positive median score. 18 items were able to obtain a median score of 3, which included *Shopping/Commercial District, Major thoroughfare and Mass Transit, Busy pedestrian and motorist activities, Filthy, dark, narrow alleyways, Congested, overcrowded, populous, Informal Economy (Street vendors, hawking), Petty Crimes, Violence and Illegal Activities (Pickpocketing, Gambling, Drug trafficking and Prostitution), Light Rail Transit (LRT Lines 1 and 2), Noisy, shabby, unclean, and polluted, Affordable goods and emporiums, retail, wholesale items, Fiesta, Popular Devotions and Traditions, University Belt, Poverty, Slums, Informal Settlements, Beggars, Street Children, Fake Documents/Counterfeit Items, Electronic goods, printing press, furniture shops, shoe marts, restaurants, Jeepneys, and Plazas (Plaza Miranda, Plaza Carriedo, Plaza Sta. Cruz)*. These items are mostly about the physical attributes of the study site (which are mostly negative features), landmarks, local culture and customs and its history as a commercial district.

Consequently, it is important to note that the items that have garnered a low mean score are associators that pertain to the history of the site being an old Japanese settlement, or its nickname as the “*Little Tokyo*” or “*Ginza of Manila*” due to the presence of bazaars run by Japanese people during the Spanish and American Occupation, the former names of the streets, which include *Calle Iris, Calle Azcarraga, Calle*

Dulumbayan, Calle Salcedo, the movie houses and theatres along the streets, its significance as a battle ground during World War II, and the former route of the Tranvia line and horse-drawn carriages in the area.

2. Relationship to demographic profile of respondents

As the data was obtained from a non-random sample, potential relationships between the demographic profile with regards to the median responses can only be assessed. Thus, this section does not make use of inferential tests for this analysis. The tables below show the potential trends of median scores with at least 1 or below with respect to place of residence and length of residency.

Place of Residence

#	ASSOCIATOR	Group 1 Median (Outside Manila)	Group 2 Median (Within Manila)
6	Sociohistorical: Sites of important people and events (Mga lugar kung saan naganap ang mahahalagang pangyayari at mga tao)	1	2
12	Movie houses / theatres, cultural arts, and vaudeilles (Mga sinehan, sining pangkultura, at teatro/tanghalan)	1	1
16	Battle of Manila, World War II (Labanan sa Maynila, Ikalawang Digmaang Pandaigdig)	1	0
17	Renamed Streets ex. Calle Iris, Calle Azcarraga, Calle Dulumbayan, Calle Salcedo (Mga pinalitang pangalan ng mga kalye)	1	1
18	Japanese Bazaar, Japanese settlements	0	-1
22	Tranvia and Horse-drawn Carriages (Tranvia at mga Kalesa)	1	1
28	Marcos Era-projects, Martial law, First Quarter Storm (Proyekto noong panahon ni Marcos, Sr., Batas Militar, Sigwa ng Unang Sangkapat)	1	1
30	Little Tokyo/Ginza of Manila	0	0
34	Buildings and Facilities Designed by Prominent Architects (Mga gusali at pasilidad na dinisensyo ng mga tanyag na arkitekto)	1	2
35	Protection of illegal vending (Lagay, proteksyon ng ilegal na pagbebenta/paghahanap-buhay)	15	3

Table 2. Relationship of selected associators to place of residence

The presented table provides insights into the potential correlation between the place of residence and the corresponding median scores obtained by respondents. Notably, items related to the role of the study site during the colonial period garnered comparatively lower scores. However, respondents residing within Manila demonstrated higher median scores for these particular items, particularly those associators that pertain to the historical and cultural aspects of the study site. Conversely, respondents residing outside of Manila exhibited lower median scores for the same items.

The observed pattern suggests that individuals living within Manila possess a deeper awareness and understanding of the historical and cultural significance associated with the study site. This is reflected in their higher median scores for items related to the

site's role during the colonial period. Moreover, certain local practices specific to Manila, such as "lagay" (referring to the protection of illegal vending), are terminologies that resonate more strongly with respondents residing within the city.

These findings highlight the influence of place of residence on the respondents' familiarity with and appreciation of the historical and cultural dimensions of the study site. The differential levels of awareness and knowledge observed between residents of Manila and those residing outside the city emphasize the importance of local context and lived experiences in shaping perceptions and interpretations of a specific urban area.

Length of Residency

#	ASSOCIATOR	Group 1 (5 years)	Group 2 (5 - 10 years)	Group 3 (10 above)	Group 99 (Not Applicable)
6	Sociohistorical: Sites of important people and events (Mga lugar kung saan naganap ang mahahalagang pangyayari at mga tao)	1.5	2	2	1
7	Downtown Area / Red light district	1	1.5	2	2
12	Movie houses / theatres, cultural arts, and vaudevilles (Mga sinehan, sining pangkultura, at teatro/tanghalan)	0	0	1	1
16	Battle of Manila, World War II (Labanan sa Maynila, Ikalawang Digmaang Pandaigdig)	-0.5	0	1	1
17	Renamed Streets ex. Calle Iris, Calle Azcarraga, Calle Dulumbayan, Calle Salcedo (Mga pinalitang pangalan ng mga kalye)	1	2	2	0
18	Japanese Bazaar, Japanese settlements	-2	-1	-1	0
22	Tranvia and Horse-drawn Carriages (Tranvia at mga Kalesa)	0.5	1	1	1
25	Economic center after Escolta (Sentro ng komersyo pagkatapos ng Escolta)	2	1.5	3	2
26	Sociopolitical Organizations and Movements, Rallies and Demonstrations (Mga organisasyong at kilusang sosyopolitikal)	2	2	2	1
28	Marcos Era-projects, Martial law, First Quarter Storm (Proyekto noong panahon ni Marcos, Sr., Batas Militar, Sigwa ng Unang Sangkapat)	-0.5	0	1	1
30	Little Tokyo/Ginza of Manila	-1.5	0	0	0
34	Buildings and Facilities Designed by Prominent Architects (Mga gusali at pasilidad na dinisensyo ng mga tanyag na arkitekto)	1.5	2	3	1

Table 3. Relationship of selected associators to length of residency
The provided table offers valuable insights into the potential correlation between median scores and the length of residency, distinguishing between individuals residing within Manila and those residing outside the city. Notably, Group 1, comprising respondents with shorter periods of residency within Manila, exhibits relatively lower median scores compared to the other three groups. Conversely, respondents who have resided within Manila for more than 10 years tend to obtain higher median scores, indicating a stronger alignment between their perceptions and the images presented.

It is noteworthy that the median scores of individuals who lived outside of Manila ranged from 0 to 2. This suggests a comparatively weaker correspondence between the

images and the experiences of those with no direct residency connection to the study site. Within this section, the associators reported by respondents encompass various elements tied to the history of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. These associators include references to the remaining architectural structures designed by renowned architects, as well as socio-cultural resources such as movie houses and vaudevilles. Additionally, the study site's role as a significant historic commercial center within Manila's urban fabric emerges as a prominent theme. The inclusion of these associators reflects the multifaceted character of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip and the diverse aspects that contribute to its perception among respondents.

3. *Are there any additional things you would like to add regarding the image and/or identity of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip?*

Various responses were gathered in relation to the abovementioned question, encompassing a range of themes and aspects associated with the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Noteworthy observations include references to the presence of *secondhand books* and the *healthcare industry*, which incorporates alternative healing practices such as *manghihiilot (traditional Filipino massage)*, *gayuma (love potions)*, *herbal medicines*, and *Chinese medicine*. Additionally, the strip was highlighted as a *gateway to Manila* through its *bus terminals*, and the *Odeon Mall* and *Isetann Mall* emerged as distinct landmarks mentioned by respondents. Moreover, there were indications of *darkness* and *staticness*, possibly alluding to the lack of vibrancy or dynamic activity perceived in the area.

It is crucial to acknowledge that this question provided an opportunity for respondents to express their sentiments *regarding potential improvements and revitalization* of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Several suggestions centered around *policy changes*, such as *street clean-ups*, *restoration of old buildings*, and *the provision of adequate vending spaces for informal vendors or hawkers*. Additionally, respondents emphasized the importance of *heightened security measures* to address issues related to *petty crimes and local syndicates* operating within the area. These sentiments reflect the respondents' aspirations for positive transformations and enhanced livability within the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

D. Visual Perception Ratings

This section of the study focuses on the exploration of the visual perception held by the respondents with regard to the present landscape character of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, employing a set of images obtained from Google Images. The participants were asked to evaluate the degree of correspondence between these images and their personal experiences and perceptions of the present Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. To facilitate this assessment, a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 was employed, allowing respondents to assign a numerical score indicative of the level of correspondence between the images and their subjective understanding of the study site.

1. Image 1: Carriedo Street Crowded with People and Informal Vendors

Figure 15. Carriedo Street. Photo credits: Alamy, Raya Capulong, ABS-CBN News

The photo above exhibits a common scene of Carriedo Street during peak seasons, where the thoroughfare is teeming with an abundance of individuals and street vendors. The visual composition also captures the convergence of light vehicles, including motorcycles and tricycles, amidst the flow of pedestrian traffic. In the analysis of respondents who identified this image as representative of their present-day perception of Carriedo Street, a significant number acknowledged the **densely populated and**

congested nature of the locale. Their descriptions encompassed terms such as *"overly crowded," "siksikan na mga tao" (crowded with people), "masikip" (constricted), and "maraming tao" (numerous individuals)*. Moreover, several participants explicitly drew attention to the prevalent presence of **street vendors** and stalls adorning the streetscape, where diverse commodities are on offer. They referred to such phenomena as *"maraming bilihan na naka pwesto o bangketa" (a multitude of shops/stalls on the sidewalk), "mga nagtitinda" (vendors), and "tiyange na mura ang mga bilihan" (bargain stalls)*. Additionally, the area was frequently characterized as a vibrant **shopping hub**, indicated by references to *"mga pamilihan" (markets), "maraming tindahan" (numerous shops), and "trading."*

While the absence of audio stimuli accompanying the photograph precluded a direct assessment, respondents vocalized the pervading atmosphere of **noise and disorder** through terms such as *"maingay" (noisy), "magulo" (disorganized), and "gulo" (chaotic)*. This observation aligned with their collective identification of **traffic congestion** as a salient predicament within the locale, denoted by references to *"trapik" (traffic) and "pagsiksikan ng mga transpo" (vehicle congestion)*.

An additional thematic thread gleaned from the respondents' feedback pertains to the augmented **pedestrian activity and foot traffic** in the area. The high influx of individuals on foot, along with the conspicuous presence of pedestrians, featured prominently in their accounts. Descriptions encompassed phrases such as *"maraming tao at maliliit na tindahan ang aking nakikita" (a multitude of individuals and small shops), "dami ng tao at sari-saring mga kiosks" (a multitude of individuals and diverse kiosks), and "volume people going to Quiapo church every Friday."* Correspondingly, some respondents expressed apprehensions regarding **safety** within the vicinity, citing concerns about petty crimes like pickpocketing and the presence of *"masamang loob" (bad elements or criminals)*. Consequently, while the area is regarded as a breeding ground for local syndicates and other nefarious entities, its **proximity to the Quiapo Church** imbues it with a degree of sanctity. Overall, the majority of participants highlighted adverse aspects of the **environmental conditions** prevailing within the locale, employing terms such as *"mabaho" (malodorous), "madumi" (unclean), and "polluted."* Furthermore, participants employed expressions such as *"hindi maganda ang environment" (unpleasant environment), "matao, masikip, madumi" (crowded,*

constricted, unclean), and "magulo, mabaho" (chaotic, malodorous) inducting their negative impressions of the place.

Median Scores of Respondents

IMAGE 1	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	6	3
2	4	2
3	9	4.5
4	39	19.5
5	142	71
TOTAL	200	100.00%
MEDIAN		5
QUARTILE 1		4
QUARTILE 3		5
IQR		1

Table 4. Median Scores of Respondents for Image 1

6 people answered that the first image does not match with their present perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip; whereas 142 people or 71% of respondents rated the first image with a score of 5. Based on the table above, the median score of respondents in Image 1 is 5, which shows that the image highly matches their current perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo strip at present.

PLACE OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Outside Manila	5
Within Manila	5

Table 5. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to place of residency for Image 1

The median score for respondents in both groups of places of residency is 5, showing that the image matches their experiences with the current Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Regardless of whether the respondents lived outside or within Manila, their perceptions of the images with respect to their present perception of the study site are the same.

LENGTH OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Group 1 (less than 5 years)	5
Group 2 (5 to 10 years)	5
Group 3 (More than 10 years)	5
Group 4 Not Applicable	5

Table 6. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to length of residency for Image 1

The median score for respondents in all groups pertaining to the length of residency of respondents is 5, meaning that the image coincides their personal encounters with the existing Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Regardless of whether the respondents lived longer or shorter outside or within Manila, their perceptions of the images with regards to their present perception of the study site are the same.

Image 2: Movie Posters of X-Rated and Comedy Films along Recto Avenue, with Street Vendors along its Arcaded Walkways

Figure 16. Recto Avenue. Photo credits: Sidney Snoeck, Guerrero Lester

The image above depicts an afternoon scene along Recto Avenue showing movie posters of X-rated and local comedy films against a backdrop of old theatres, and a darkened arcaded walkway filled with street vendors. Among the responses that highly matched with the photo, one recurrent theme emanating from the respondents' perceptions was the concept of **urban decay**. Descriptive terms such as "*decrepit buildings*," "*dilapidated structures*," and "*mess of cables*" underscored the deteriorating architectural fabric of Recto Avenue, lending it a distinctive character. Additionally, observations pertaining to **environmental conditions** yielded descriptors such as "*dirty*

walls/concrete," "improper maintenance of buildings," and "mausok." These references underscore the challenges posed by neglect and inadequate upkeep, impacting the overall aesthetic quality of the area.

With regards to Recto Avenue's role as one of Manila's commercial centers, the respondents cited **commercial establishments** such as "food chains," "various stores," and "commercial space." These establishments, often offering affordable goods, contribute to the economic vibrancy and accessibility of the locale. In relation to this, the presence of **street vendors** emerged as a prominent theme, as indicated by participants' references to "sidewalk vendors," "informal vendors," and "unorganized stalls." These vendors, situated along the arcaded walkways, add vitality to the urban fabric while contributing to the commercial ecosystem of Recto Avenue. However, among these elements within Recto's urban ecosystem, the respondents highlighted instances of **illicit activities**, such as the *production of counterfeit documents and the presence of illegal vendors*. The mention of "fake certificates/diplomas" and "prostitutes operating near old theaters" draws attention to the complex dynamics and social issues within the urban landscape.

With regards to the previous terms relating to old theaters, respondents acknowledged the presence of **old movie theaters**, emphasizing their historical significance. References to "old theaters," "cinemas showing porn," and "bold movies/x-rated films" shed light on the cultural and entertainment dimensions associated with Recto Avenue. In accordance with this, the respondents' remarks evoked a sense of **nostalgia**, with mentions of "nostalgic theater houses," "old movie houses," and "rare hand-painted signages in older art style." These observations underscore the cultural and historical significance of Recto Avenue, resonating with individuals familiar with its past. On the flipside and in relation to illegal activities operating within the area, references to **red light districts** and associated activities were apparent in respondents' statements. Terms such as "pornography," "sleazy," and "bold movies/x-rated films" hinted at the perception of certain areas along Recto Avenue as spaces associated with adult entertainment and potential safety concerns.

Lastly, the **densely populated nature** of the locale was frequently mentioned, with terms such as "crowded streets," "packed establishments," and "cramped spaces" highlighting the bustling atmosphere. Such crowd density reinforces Recto Avenue's

role as a vibrant hub of activity and commerce. Converging with this sentiment includes references to **transportation and traffic-related concerns**. Participants cited the presence of "jeepneys," "loading/unloading areas," and the proximity to "LRT stations." These references highlight the transportation infrastructure and the resulting challenges associated with congestion and pedestrian movement.

Median Scores of Respondents

IMAGE 2	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	12	6
2	7	3.5
3	23	11.5
4	50	25
5	108	54
TOTAL	200	100%
MEDIAN	5	
QUARTILE 1	4	
QUARTILE 3	5	
IQR	1	

Table 7. Median Scores of Respondents for Image 2

Out of the respondents, 12 individuals indicated that the second image does not correspond to their current perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Conversely, 108 respondents, accounting for 54% of the total, gave the second image a rating of 5. According to the information provided in the table, the median score for Image 2 is 5. This suggests that the image closely aligns with the participants' present perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

PLACE OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Outside Manila	5
Within Manila	5

Table 8. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to place of residency for Image 2

Both groups of respondents, regardless of their place of residency, gave a median score of 5 for the images. This indicates that the images accurately represent their current experiences with the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Whether the respondents lived in Manila or outside of it, their perceptions of the images in relation to their present perception of the study site were consistent.

LENGTH OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Group 1 (less than 5 years)	4.5
Group 2 (5 to 10 years)	4
Group 3 (More than 10 years)	5
Group 4 Not Applicable	4

Table 9. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to length of residency for Image 2

The median scores for respondents in all residency groups, whether they lived in Manila or outside of it, ranged from 4 to 5. This suggests that the image aligns with their individual experiences of the current Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. There is no discernible pattern in the median scores based on the length of residency, indicating that the image's match to their personal encounters with the area is consistent regardless of how long they have lived there.

**Image 3: Arcaded Walkway during the Day and Night along Rizal Avenue
Showing Posters of Prostitutes alongside a Motel**

Figure 17. Arcaded walkway in Rizal Avenue. Photo credits: Sidney Snoeck, Walk With AL Youtube Channel

The image above shows a day and evening scene of an arcaded walkway along Rizal Avenue showing pictures of prostitutes alongside a motel. Some of the elements that

can be visibly seen within this image set include actual prostitutes roaming around the area, and street vendors along the walkway. Among the responses which expressed congruence with their personal experiences to this photo is the **commercial congestion and variety** that can be found within the area. The respondents noted the congested nature of the area, with numerous businesses and vendors offering a wide range of products and services, with terms including *Masikip na daanan (congested walkway)*, *Maraming kainan at mga natutulog na street dwellers sa daan (many eateries and street dwellers)*, *Maraming tindahan sa bangketa (many stores on the sidewalk)*, *Sidewalk vendors, nagtitinda, kabi-kabilang nagtitinda (sidewalk vendors, various vendors)*, *Madaming nagbebenta sa gilid na nakaharang sa daan (many sellers obstructing the path)*, and *Maraming pahilot at alahasan near establishments (many massage services and jewelers near establishments)*. In addition to this, they observed the presence of hotels, inns, motels, and various street vendors selling different items. In relation to this, the respondents highlighted the prevalence of **sidewalk vendors and informal businesses** occupying the walkway. They described the vendors as unorganized and occupying space that should be allocated for pedestrian passage. The variety of goods and services offered by these vendors, ranging from electronics to fake documents, was also mentioned.

The place is also noted for its dark reputation as a **red-light district** and the prevalence of **petty crimes and local syndicates**. The image evoked associations with a red-light district due to the presence of motels, posters depicting prostitutes, and the general atmosphere after dark. This perception was reinforced by the respondents' comments on the reputation of the area for adult entertainment, with terms such as *Prostitutes*, *pokpok (prostitutes)*, *Pornographic images and movies, bold/x-rated movie, Sex dens, Nude Show/Cinemas, Pugad ng prostitusyon (prostitution dens)*. The respondents also cited **safety concerns** when passing through the area. The narrow and dark alleys, coupled with references to illicit activities, including prostitution, counterfeit document fabrication, and adult cinemas, raised concerns about safety and security within the location. The presence of pickpockets and a general perception of danger after dark was also mentioned. Notable terms that were mentioned fitting this theme include *masikip na eskinita (dark and narrow alley)*, *Madilim, nakakatakot, delikado (dark, scary, dangerous)*, *unsafe sidewalk*, and *Shady shops*. In spite of the presence of these

dangerous elements within the vicinity, the respondents noted the **connection of the area to transportation hubs** such as Recto and Carriedo Stations, as well as **its proximity to schools and educational institutions**. This proximity to key transportation and educational facilities shaped the environment and activities in the area.

Lastly, the image evoked a **negative impression** with the respondents citing its **present environmental conditions** and **the urban decay and dilapidation** of old, but architecturally and culturally significant buildings in the area, and the general landscape character of the vicinity. The environment was described as crowded, with narrow and dark alleys, often lacking proper lighting. The presence of street dwellers and a bustling street life contributed to the overall ambiance. Moreover, references were made to the dilapidated buildings, historical elements such as old posters and signs, and the overall shabby appearance of the area. These elements contributed to a sense of urban decay and added character to the location.

Median Scores of Respondents

IMAGE 3	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	15	7.5
2	11	5.5
3	16	8
4	46	23
5	112	56
TOTAL	200	100%
MEDIAN	5	
QUARTILE 1	4	
QUARTILE 3	5	
IQR	1	

Table 10. Median Scores of Respondents for Image 3

A total of 15 respondents indicated that the third image does not correspond to their current perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Conversely, 112 individuals, accounting for 56% of the respondents, gave the second image a rating of 5. According to the provided table, the median score for Image 3 is 5, indicating a strong alignment between the image and the participants' present perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo strip.

PLACE OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Outside Manila	5
Within Manila	5

Table 11. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to place of residency for Image 3

The table above reveals a median score of 5 among respondents from different residency groups, indicating a congruence between the image presented and their personal encounters with the present state of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Importantly, this similarity persists irrespective of whether the respondents reside within the boundaries of Manila or beyond, signifying a consistency in their perceptions of the images vis-à-vis their present understanding of the study site.

LENGTH OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Group 1 (less than 5 years)	4.5
Group 2 (5 to 10 years)	4
Group 3 (More than 10 years)	5
Group 4 Not Applicable	5

Table 12. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to length of residency for Image 3

The analysis of median scores across all groups based on respondents' length of residency reveals a range of 4 to 5, indicating a noteworthy correspondence between the depicted image and their individual experiences of the present state of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Notably, no discernible trend emerges from the median scores concerning respondents' length of residency, irrespective of whether they resided within or outside Manila.

Image 4: Rizal Avenue Traffic during Inclement Weather depicting a Homeless Family along the Center Island, and a Brightened Section of the Avenue

Figure 18. Rainy evening in Rizal Avenue. Photo credits: Pinoy Joyride

The image set above depicts Rizal Avenue during inclement weather, showing pictures of traffic congestion, and a homeless family seeking shelter along the center island, and a brightened section of the avenue nearing Carriedo Street. Based on the comments of respondents whose experiences matches that of the image, the predominant theme relates to the **heavy traffic congestion and disorganization** experienced along Rizal Avenue, particularly during rush hour and inclement weather. Respondents mentioned the presence of numerous vehicles, such as jeepneys and cars, leading to slow movement and disorderly traffic conditions. Some terms that fall within this theme include *Traffic, congested road, Slow movement, Disorderly traffic, Rush hour, Heavy traffic, Maraming sasakyan (many vehicles)*. In addition to this, the respondents stressed the **importance of transportation infrastructure**. The image includes references to the LRT (Light Rail Transit) system, specifically LRT 1, which runs along Rizal Avenue. Respondents mentioned the significance of the LRT as a means of transportation, noting its association with the area and its impact on traffic conditions,

with terms such as *LRT Line 1 (Light Rail Transit)*, *Transport hub*, *public transportation*, and *Sakayan (term for public transportation)*.

Another emergent theme based on the set of responses on this image set is the presence of the **informal economy and street vendors** along Rizal Avenue. References were made to street vendors and stalls located along Rizal Avenue, particularly on the sidewalks. Respondents mentioned the presence of vendors selling street food, as well as the occurrence of informal commerce, such as selling goods on traveling carts or sidewalk displays, with terms such as *street vendors*, *street food*, *travelling sidewalk vendors*, *stalls*, and *informal commerce*. In contrast, several respondents mentioned the presence of **squatter settlements or informal settlements** along Rizal Avenue. This highlights the issue of housing and the presence of marginalized communities in the area, with the respondents citing terminologies including *squatter areas*, *informal settlements*, *mga pulubi or beggars*, *street children*, and *slums o barong-barong*.

Lastly, the respondents cited the presence of dimly lit sidewalks and brightened road. This contrast was noted by respondents, emphasizing the difference in lighting conditions and the potential safety concerns associated with the darker areas, using terms such as “*madilim na eskinita*” at “*maaliwalas na kalsada*”. Among the respondents, however, include the **discord between their personal perception of development and changes over time within Rizal Avenue**. Some respondents commented on the perceived improvements and changes that have taken place over time. They mentioned renovations, furnishing of bridge pillars, and a more modernized appearance compared to their previous experiences. Alternatively, some respondents believe that this area is not part of Rizal Avenue, due to the differing appearances of LRT Columns, and contrast between dimly lit and bright areas.

Median Scores of Respondents

IMAGE 4	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	22	11
2	14	7
3	26	13
4	37	18.5
5	101	50.5
TOTAL	200	100%
MEDIAN	5	
QUARTILE 1	3	
QUARTILE 3	5	
IQR	2	

Table 13. Median Scores of Respondents for Image 4

The table above reveals that a total of 22 participants expressed that the fourth image did not correspond to their present perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, whereas 102 individuals, constituting 50.5% of the respondents, assigned a score of 5 to the second image. Analyzing the provided table, the median score for Image 4 is determined to be 5, thereby indicating a strong concurrence between the image and the participants' current perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo strip.

PLACE OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Outside Manila	4
Within Manila	5

Table 14. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to place of residency for Image 4

The comparison of median scores reveals a notable disparity between respondents residing within Manila and those residing outside of it. Specifically, individuals living within Manila exhibited a higher median score, indicating a stronger alignment between their perception and the prevailing landscape character of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

LENGTH OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Group 1 (less than 5 years)	4.5
Group 2 (5 to 10 years)	5
Group 3 (More than 10 years)	5
Group 4 Not Applicable	4

Table 15. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to length of residency for Image 4

The analysis of median scores across all groups based on respondents' length of residency reveals a range spanning from 4 to 5, indicative of a substantial

correspondence between the portrayed image and their individual encounters with the present state of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Notably, no discernible pattern emerges from the median scores in relation to respondents' length of residency, regardless of whether they reside within or outside Manila.

Image 5: Former Theatres along Rizal Avenue Converted into a Park Mall and Casino, and Motel

Figure 19. Former Universal and Ever theatres in Rizal Avenue. Photo credits: Riel Diala

The image set above shows two former theaters, the Universal Theater, and the Ever Theatre, converted into new commercial establishments, such as a park mall, casino, and motel along Rizal Avenue. Based on the insights of respondents, an **abundance of hotels and commercial establishments** remained the prevalent theme as it consistently highlights the prevalence of hotels and various establishments in the vicinity of the former theater along Rizal Avenue. Multiple respondents emphasize the significant presence of hotels, often mentioning the successive nature of these establishments. Additionally, references are made to street vendors and dwellers coexisting with these commercial entities. Among the insights that the respondents provided include *Maraming hotel dito at kadalasan may mga street dwellers na naninirahan sa kalsada (there are many hotels here, and usually there are street dwellers living on the streets),*

*Madaming mga establisemento at tindahan (many establishments and shops), and yung lumang sinehan na Universal (the hotel and the old Universal theater. Consequently, the responses also reflect the perception of a **congested and crowded environment** surrounding the converted theater. Respondents describe the area as overcrowded, with excessive foot traffic and vehicular movement. Congestion is further attributed to the presence of numerous establishments and shops, particularly budget motels/hotels. The proximity of the location to the LRT station is also highlighted as a contributing factor to the congestion. Some responses citing this emerging theme include the terms *siksikan, crowded, maraming tao, chaotic, maraming mamimili, tindera at mga bilihan, at lugar na malapit sa LRT at Carriedo.**

In line with this, respondents cited the presence of **sidewalk vendors**, and **dimly lit and dilapidated environment** along Rizal Avenue. Sidewalk vendors play a significant role in the local landscape within Avenida Rizal surrounding the former theater. The responses indicate the coexistence of various establishments and sidewalk vendors, with reference to their diversity and presence along the sidewalks. However, there are also mentions of undesirable aspects such as vendors occupying the pathway or engaging in illicit activities, including the presence of beggars, snatchers, and prostitutes. Terms justifying this theme from the gathered data include *Mga sidewalk vendor, pulubi, mga snatcher at prostitute (sidewalk vendors, beggars, snatchers, and prostitutes), Pagtawid at pagbibili sa mga sidewalk vendors (crossing and buying from sidewalk vendors), Madaming mga tindahan sa paligid (many shops around), and Mga tindera na hindi kaaya-aya at sinasakop ang daanman (undesirable vendors occupying the pathway).* Consistent with this, perceptions of a dimly lit and dilapidated environment are expressed by respondents. The descriptions highlight the lack of sufficient lighting, creating an atmosphere that is deemed sketchy or unsafe. The responses further emphasize concerns regarding the cleanliness of the area, along with disorganized and unsafe signages and billboards. Examples of responses that coincide with this sentiment include *Madilim na mga iskinita/bangketa (dark alleys/sidewalks), Dimly lit pedestrian lane, old and dilapidated cinemas, The establishments have less lighting that makes it feel like a sketchy shop, Disorganized and unsafe signages and billboards, Madumi, maraming tao, mga illegal vendors (dirty, many people, illegal vendors).*

Median Scores of Respondents

IMAGE 5	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	19	9.5
2	16	8
3	23	11.5
4	38	19
5	104	52
TOTAL	200	100%
MEDIAN		5
QUARTILE 1		3
QUARTILE 3		5
IQR		2

Table 16. Median Scores of Respondents for Image 5

A total of 19 respondents indicated that the fifth image does not align with their present perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, while 104 individuals, accounting for 52% of the respondents, assigned a rating of 5 to the second image. Considering the information presented in the table above, the median score for Image 5 is determined to be 5, signifying a strong connection between the image and the respondents' current perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo strip.

PLACE OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Outside Manila	5
Within Manila	5

Table 17. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to place of residency for Image 5

The findings, as shown in the table above, demonstrate that the median score of 5 for respondents in both residency groups indicates a notable similarity between the depicted image and their experiential understanding of the current state of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Remarkably, this alignment remains consistent regardless of whether participants resided within or outside Manila, highlighting a convergence in their perceptions of the images concerning their present perception of the study site.

LENGTH OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Group 1 (less than 5 years)	4
Group 2 (5 to 10 years)	5
Group 3 (More than 10 years)	5
Group 4 Not Applicable	4

Table 18. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to length of residency for Image 5

The analysis of median scores across all groups of respondents with respect to their length of residency reveals a range spanning from 4 to 5, indicating a substantial alignment between the depicted image and their individual experiences of the existing Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Notably, participants with a residency of less than 5 years and those residing outside of Manila scored lower compared to individuals with a longer duration of residence within the city, suggesting a potential correlation between length of residency and the extent to which the images correspond to their present perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

Image 6: Plaza Miranda Filled with People and Street Vendors

Figure 20. Plaza Miranda. Photo credits: Julie Gilbero, Alamy

The above image shows Plaza Miranda and Quiapo Church filled with people and street vendors during peak hours. Among the cohort of responses, themes of **congestion and overcrowding** remain prevalent in their answers. Terms and phrases such as *"overly crowded," "siksikan," "madaming tao," "matao,"* and *"mainit"* (*crowded, crowded, lots of people, crowded, crowded*) consistently highlight the theme of congestion and overcrowding in Plaza Miranda. Respondents mention the lack of proper walkways, the presence of numerous street vendors, and the influx of devotees, particularly during religious events like the Pista ng Nazareno. The crowded environment is described as

chaotic, noisy, and difficult to navigate. In addition to this, the **presence of street vendors** is a recurring theme, with terms like *"mga tindera," "nagtitinda," "vendor," "paninda"* (*vendors, selling, vendor, merchandise*) being used throughout the responses. Street vendors selling various items such as religious articles, food, plants, and counterfeit goods are described as scattered, occupying sidewalks and impeding pedestrian movement. The vendors contribute to the crowded atmosphere but also add vibrancy to the area. Deriving from this theme emerges the concept of **disorder and chaos**, with terms such as *"magulo," "walang maayos na lugar," "no order," "chaotic," and "illegal vendors"* suggest a sense of disorder and informality in Plaza Miranda. Further, the respondents expressed concerns about the lack of proper infrastructure, including pedestrian lanes, and the presence of illegal vendors occupying public spaces.

Consequently, the place being in **close proximity to Quiapo Church** is also a recurring theme among the responses. The Quiapo Church is frequently mentioned as a prominent landmark in Plaza Miranda. Respondents refer to it as *"Quiapo church," "Simbahan ng Quiapo," and "Church,"* highlighting its significance as a religious site and a pilgrimage destination. The presence of devotees and the observation of religious practices, such as the procession of the Black Nazarene, are associated with the church. Finally, the responses reveal that the image of Plaza Miranda is linked to **cultural and commercial activity**. Respondents mention the sale of religious items, fortune tellers, eateries, and market-like settings. Terms like *"religious markets," "commercial establishments," "informal vendors," and "knotted wires"* reflect the diverse range of activities and offerings in the area.

Median Scores of Respondents

IMAGE 6	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	14	7
2	13	6.5
3	4	2
4	23	11.5
5	146	73
TOTAL	200	100%
MEDIAN	5	
QUARTILE 1	4	
QUARTILE 3	5	
IQR	1	

Table 19. Median Scores of Respondents for Image 6

Within the cohort of respondents, 14 individuals reported that the sixth image does not align with their current perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. In contrast, a significant majority of 146 participants, accounting for 73% of the sample, assigned a rating of 5 to the second image. Consistent with the data provided in the table, the calculated median score for Image 6 is 5, indicating a strong relationship between the image and the participants' present perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo strip.

PLACE OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Outside Manila	5
Within Manila	5

Table 20. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to place of residency for Image 6

The results indicate that the median score of 5 for respondents in both residency groups implies a significant concurrence between the image presented and their lived experiences of the present condition of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Remarkably, this alignment persists irrespective of whether the participants resided within or outside the city of Manila, suggesting that their perceptions of the images, in relation to their present perception of the study site, exhibit uniformity across different residency locations.

LENGTH OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Group 1 (less than 5 years)	5
Group 2 (5 to 10 years)	5
Group 3 (More than 10 years)	5
Group 4 Not Applicable	5

Table 21. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to length of residency for Image 6

The findings reveal that the median score of 5 among respondents in all residency duration groups signifies a substantial agreement between the depicted image and their individual experiences of the current state of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Importantly, this consistency in perception remains irrespective of the length of residency, whether longer or shorter, and regardless of whether individuals reside within or outside Manila.

Image 7: Rizal Avenue corner Carriedo Street

Figure 21. Rizal Avenue and Carriedo Street. Photo credits: Riel Diala, Google Earth Street Imagery

The final images depict Rizal Avenue along the corner of Carriedo street. From the answers of the respondents whose personal experiences and encounters highly matched with the image, the theme of **transport and infrastructure** remains prevalent among the others. The intersection of Rizal Avenue and Carriedo Street exhibits a prominent transportation hub, featuring the LRT station and overhead tracks of the LRT Line 1. The area experiences high levels of traffic congestion, particularly during peak hours. Public utility vehicles, such as jeepneys, tricycles, and pedicabs, contribute to the transport flow. While the roads are wide and equipped with proper posts, there is a lack of clear lanes and stoplights. Pedestrian crossings are insufficient, necessitating improvements in pedestrian infrastructure. Covered walkways and overpasses are present, facilitating pedestrian movement. Road parking is a common occurrence, and parking space management requires attention. The presence of train tracks and a railway further emphasizes the area's significance as a transportation hub. Some terminologies from the responses that support this theme include *LRT station, lack of clear lanes, train tracks, transport flow, traffic, congestion, rush hour*. Consequently, the respondents also noted the **crowded and congested nature of the area**, citing terms such as *Many*

people, lots of pedestrians, matao (crowded), Heavy traffic, maingay (noisy), matao at masikip (crowded and cramped), Snatchers, trapik na lugar (traffic-prone area), magulo (chaotic), Lack of order, no usad (movement), lack of clear tawiran (crossings), Lack of green spaces, unpleasant walking experiences, unsafe areas, Crowded and dirty, lack of cleanliness, malinis na kalsada (clean road). Rizal Avenue corner Carriedo Street is notorious for its crowded and congested environment. The intersection witnesses heavy foot traffic and experiences substantial vehicular congestion, leading to chaotic conditions. The high volume of pedestrians and vehicles contributes to a noisy and bustling atmosphere. Safety concerns arise due to instances of theft and the lack of organized movement. The absence of clear pedestrian lanes and limited green spaces further exacerbates the challenges faced by pedestrians. The overall cleanliness of the area is suboptimal, detracting from the pleasantness of walking experiences.

The reputation of the area being a **commercial establishment and the presence of vendors** is also a recurring theme among the respondents. Rizal Avenue corner Carriedo Street is characterized by a vibrant commercial landscape. Various malls, shops, and stores, including clothing stores and electronics shops, line the streets. Sidewalk vendors, selling their goods displayed on *bilao or sako (native woven trays or sacks)*, contribute to the street market ambiance. *Ukay-ukay (secondhand clothing stalls) and arcade sidewalks* are also prevalent. The area accommodates small-time businesses and established establishments, providing a diverse range of goods and services. Notable commercial entities, such as *Puregold*, offer supermarket options. The presence of food stalls and eateries offers a variety of dining choices. However, it is worth noting the existence of *informal settlers, commonly referred to as squatters, within the vicinity*. Finally, the respondents also cited the presence of **old buildings and historically significant buildings within the area, and urban blight and dilapidated structures** which add to the present landscape character of the area depicted in the image. The ambiance of *dimly lit pedestrian lanes* adds to the distinct character of the location. *Billboards, signage, and warnings* contribute to the visual landscape of the intersection. Some individuals perceive the environment as *unsafe or intimidating* due to the *prevalence of snatchers and the lack of order*. The limited space available for traffic flow and pedestrian movement poses challenges in terms of urban planning. *Ongoing*

infrastructural improvements and changes in the area indicate the potential for future transformations.

Median Scores of Respondents

IMAGE 7	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	23	11.5
2	12	6
3	28	14
4	39	19.5
5	98	49
TOTAL	200	100.00%
MEDIAN		4
QUARTILE 1		3
QUARTILE 3		5
IQR		2

Table 22. Median Scores of Respondents for Image 7

According to the data provided, a total of 23 respondents indicated that the final image does not correspond to their current perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. In contrast, 98 individuals, accounting for 49% of the participants, awarded a rating of 5 to the second image. Based on the information presented in the table, the median score for Image 5 is determined to be 4, suggesting a moderate alignment between the image and the participants' present perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo strip.

PLACE OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Outside Manila	5
Within Manila	4

Table 23. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to place of residency for Image 8

The analysis of median scores indicates that respondents residing outside Manila exhibited a higher median score compared to those residing within Manila. This observation suggests that the perception of individuals living within Manila moderately aligns with the prevailing landscape character of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

LENGTH OF RESIDENCY	MEDIAN
Group 1 (less than 5 years)	4
Group 2 (5 to 10 years)	4.5
Group 3 (More than 10 years)	5
Group 4 Not Applicable	4

Table 24. Median Scores of Respondents in relation to length of residency for Image 7

The analysis of median scores across all groups of respondents with respect to their length of residency reveals a range spanning from 4 to 5, indicating a substantial alignment between the depicted image and their individual encounters with the existing Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Notably, participants with a residency of less than 5 years and those residing outside of Manila scored lower compared to individuals with a longer duration of residence within the city. This suggests a potential association between the length of residency and the degree of correspondence between the images and their current perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

E. Landscape Preference and Improvement

This section aims to explore the potential inclusion of various landscape elements in enhancing the open spaces and streetscapes of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, building upon the images presented in the previous section. Respondents are instructed to carefully assess and select the landscape elements that they believe can contribute to the improvement of specific areas within the study site. Furthermore, a quantitative analysis will be conducted to determine the frequency at which these landscape elements are chosen, presenting the results in the form of percentages.

The selection process involved presenting a set of images depicting different landscape elements commonly found in urban settings. These elements encompass a wide range of features, such as trees and vegetation, seating areas, pedestrian paths, lighting fixtures, public art installations, water features, and recreational amenities. Respondents were asked to carefully examine the images and indicate the landscape elements they believed should be integrated into the identified areas for improvement within the study site.

To ensure accurate analysis, the frequency of landscape elements selected by the respondents was recorded and quantified. This information was then converted into percentages to provide a clear representation of the relative popularity and desirability of each element and was presented through a bar graph. By examining these percentages, a comprehensive understanding of the landscape elements that are favored by the respondents can be obtained. The implications of this section were used in the co-design workshop session as additional insights for the participants, enabling them to create more responsive and user-friendly environments that align with the preferences of the community.

Image 1: Carriedo Street Crowded with People and Informal Vendors

Figure 22. Preferred Landscape Elements for Image 1

IMAGE 1		
LANDSCAPE ELEMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
CCTV Units	178	89
Trash Receptacles	147	73.5
Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery	147	73.5
Lamp Posts/Lighting Units	143	71.5
Pedestrian Lane	140	70
Police Outpost	137	68.5
PWD Ramps	130	65
Public Restrooms	126	63

Designated food stalls and eateries	126	63
Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks	125	62.5
Pedestrian Crossing	122	61
Wayfinding Signages	121	60.5
Bike Lane	117	58.5
Public Parking Spaces	103	51.5
PUV Lanes	98	49
Interpretative Signages and Markers	93	46.5
Information Board or Kiosk	91	45.5
Transport Bays	89	44.5
Benches	86	43
Public Art Installations	52	26
Drinking fountain	49	24.5
Water Feature	39	19.5
Bollard	37	18.5
Al Fresco/Picnic Tables	36	18
Gazebos and Pavillions	30	15
Children's Playground	18	9

Table 25. Preference of Landscape Elements in Image 1

The presented chart and table provide valuable insights into the landscape elements preferred by respondents, with regard to their potential incorporation into the depicted image of a busy and crowded Carriedo Street. The findings reveal the varying frequencies at which different landscape elements were cited by the cohort of respondents, shedding light on their preferences and priorities within the surveyed area.

Among the landscape elements assessed, CCTV Units emerged as the most prominently desired feature, with 178 individuals, or 89% of respondents, acknowledging the necessity of their inclusion within the area. This indicates a strong consensus among the surveyed population regarding the importance of surveillance and security measures in enhancing the safety and well-being of individuals within the Carriedo Street. Additional landscape elements that garnered considerable attention for potential

incorporation include *Trash Receptacles, Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery, Lamp Posts/Lighting Units, Pedestrian Lanes, Police Outposts, PWD Ramps, and Public Restrooms*. These elements received frequencies ranging from 126 to 147 respondents, representing approximately 63% to 73.5% of the total responses.

Respondents have shown moderate priority to landscape elements which includes *Designated food stalls and eateries, Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks, Pedestrian Crossing, Wayfinding Signages, Bike Lane, Public Parking Spaces, PUV Lanes, Interpretative Signages and Markers, and Information Board or Kiosk*. These elements have a range of frequency of selection of 91 to 126, which constituted 45.5 to 63% of responses among the cohort.

Conversely, landscape elements with relatively lower frequency scores include *Transport Bays, Benches, Public Art Installations, Drinking Fountains, Water Features, Bollards, Al Fresco/Picnic Tables, Gazebos, Pavilions, and Children's Playgrounds*. The selection of these elements constituted approximately 9% to 44.5% of the total responses, indicating a comparatively lower priority for their inclusion within the surveyed area.

Image 2: Movie Posters of X-Rated and Comedy Films along Recto Avenue, with Street Vendors along its Arcaded Walkways

Figure 23. Preferred Landscape Elements for Image 2

Memoryscapes in Recto-spection:
Visualizing Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoryscapes
through immersive mobile technologies and digital heritage interpretation

IMAGE 2		
LANDSCAPE ELEMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
CCTV Units	173	86.5
Trash Receptacles	160	80
Wayfinding Signages	148	74
Lamp Posts/Lighting Units	148	74
Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery	148	74
Pedestrian Lane	145	72.5
PWD Ramps	140	70
Transport Bays	138	69
Bike Lane	137	68.5
Pedestrian Crossing	135	67.5
Police Outpost	128	64
Benches	126	63
Information Board or Kiosk	125	62.5
Public Restrooms	124	62
Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks	117	58.5
PUV Lanes	116	58
Designated food stalls and eateries	104	52
Interpretative Signages and Markers	93	46.5
Public Parking Spaces	80	40
Drinking fountain	59	29.5
Bollard	49	24.5
Al Fresco/Picnic Tables	47	23.5
Public Art Installations	45	22.5
Water Feature	29	14.5
Gazebos and Pavillions	25	12.5
Children's Playground	15	7.5

Table 26. Preference of Landscape Elements in Image 2

The chart and table above demonstrate the landscape elements preferred by respondents, with respect to their potential integration into the depicted image of Recto

Avenue. The findings reveal the different preferences and priorities of respondents within the area.

Akin to the previous item, CCTV Units emerged as the most prominently desired feature, with 173 individuals, or 86.5% of respondents, signifying a strong agreement between the need for heightened security measures within the area to enhance the safety of individuals passing through Recto Avenue, given its reputation as a dangerous thoroughfare. Additionally, landscape elements that garnered a considerable amount of priority include *Trash Receptacles*, *Wayfinding Signages*, *Lamp Posts/Lighting Units*, *Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery*, *Pedestrian Lane*, *PWD Ramps*, *Transport Bays*, with frequencies of responses spanning from 138 to 160, making up 69 to 80% of answers.

On the contrary, landscape elements with relatively lower frequency scores include *Interpretative Signages and Markers*, *Public Parking Spaces*, *Drinking fountain*, *Bollard*, *Al Fresco/Picnic Tables*, *Public Art Installations*, *Water Feature*, *Gazebos and Pavilions*, and *Children's Playground*. A relatively lower priority for their inclusion within the depicted image can be drawn from the obtained frequency of these landscape elements as the selection of these elements comprised approximately 7.5% to 46.5% of the total responses.

Image 3: Arcaded Walkway during the Day and Night along Rizal Avenue Showing Posters of Prostitutes alongside a Motel

Figure 24. Preferred Landscape Elements for Image 3

IMAGE 3		
LANDSCAPE ELEMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
CCTV Units	172	86
Trash Receptacles	146	73
Lamp Posts/Lighting Units	138	69
Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery	128	64
Police Outpost	126	63
Wayfinding Signages	125	62.5
Pedestrian Lane	123	61.5
Benches	120	60
Pedestrian Crossing	114	57
Public Restrooms	110	55
PWD Ramps	110	55
Information Board or Kiosk	108	54
Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks	106	53
Bike Lane	100	50
Designated food stalls and eateries	97	48.5
Transport Bays	96	48
PUV Lanes	84	42
Interpretative Signages and Markers	75	37.5
Public Parking Spaces	64	32
Bollard	53	26.5
Drinking fountain	50	25
Al Fresco/Picnic Tables	40	20
Public Art Installations	34	17
Water Feature	20	10
Gazebos and Pavillions	17	8.5
Children's Playground	12	6

Table 27. Preference of Landscape Elements in Image 3

The previous chart and table showcase the preferred landscape elements by respondents when asked about their prospective incorporation into the image of an arcaded walkway

along Rizal Avenue. Similar to the previous items, the results indicate the preferences and priorities of the survey participants within the area.

CCTV Units remained as the recurring most prominently desired feature, with 172 individuals, or 86% of respondents, like previous responses. This indicates that safety and security remain one of the highest priorities of respondents who selected this landscape element. In addition, the other landscape elements that garnered a considerable amount of priority include *Trash Receptacles, Lamp Posts/Lighting Units, Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery, Police Outpost, Wayfinding Signages, Pedestrian Lane, and Benches* with frequencies of responses ranges from 120 to 146, constituting 60 to 73% of responses.

Consequently, the landscape elements with relatively lower priority due to its low frequency scores include *Interpretative Signages and Markers, Public Parking Spaces, Bollard, Drinking fountain, Al Fresco/Picnic Tables, Public Art Installations, Water Feature, Gazebos and Pavilions, and Children's Playground*, as their frequencies ranged from 12 to 75, making up only 6 to 37.5% of answers.

Image 4: Rizal Avenue Traffic during Inclement Weather depicting a Homeless Family along the Center Island, and a Brightened Section of the Avenue

Figure 25. Preferred Landscape Elements for Image 4

Memoryscapes in Recto-spection:
Visualizing Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoryscapes
through immersive mobile technologies and digital heritage interpretation

IMAGE 4		
LANDSCAPE ELEMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
CCTV Units	171	85.5
Pedestrian Crossing	138	69
Pedestrian Lane	135	67.5
Trash Receptacles	133	66.5
Trees/Shrubbery	133	66.5
Lamp Posts/Lighting Units	132	66
Bike Lane	131	65.5
Wayfinding Signages	128	64
Transport Bays	127	63.5
Police Outpost	126	63
PUV Lanes	118	59
PWD Ramps	117	58.5
Information Board or Kiosk	107	53.5
Benches	94	47
Public Restrooms	93	46.5
Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks	75	37.5
Public Parking Spaces	62	31
Designated food stalls and eateries	59	29.5
Bollard	54	27
Public Art Installations	39	19.5
Drinking fountain	35	17.5
Al Fresco/Picnic Tables	32	16
Water Feature	20	10
Children's Playground	15	7.5
Interpretative Signages and Markers	14	7
Gazebos and Pavillions	11	5.5

Table 27. Preference of Landscape Elements in Image 4

The chart and table above give a glimpse into the preferred landscape elements preferred by respondents when asked about which elements can they include in an image depicting traffic in Rizal Avenue during inclement weather. The results show the

varying preferences and priorities of the respondents based on the varying frequency scores of each landscape element.

Consistent with the other findings, CCTV Units emerged as the most prominently desired feature, with 171 individuals, or 85.5% of respondents, acknowledging the necessity of their inclusion within the area. This shows that there is a need to reinforce safety and security measures within the area based on their responses. Additional landscape elements that garnered considerable attention for potential incorporation include *Trash Receptacles*, *Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery*, *Lamp Posts/Lighting Units*, *Pedestrian Lanes*, *Pedestrian Crossing*, and *Wayfinding Signages*. These elements received frequencies ranging from 128 to 138 respondents, representing approximately 64% to 69% of the total responses. Landscape elements with relatively lower frequency scores, on the other hand, include *Designated food stalls and eateries*, *Bollard*, *Public Art Installations*, *Drinking fountain*, *Al Fresco/Picnic Tables*, *Water Feature*, *Children's Playground*, *Interpretative Signages and Markers*, and *Gazebos and Pavillions*. The selection of these elements constituted approximately 5.5% to 29.5% of the total responses, indicating a comparatively lower priority for their inclusion within the surveyed area.

Image 5: Former Theatres along Rizal Avenue Converted into a Park Mall and Casino, and Motel

Figure 26. Preferred Landscape Elements for Image 5

IMAGE 5		
LANDSCAPE ELEMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
CCTV Units	164	82
Trash Receptacles	135	67.5
Lamp Posts/Lighting Units	133	66.5
Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery	130	65
Wayfinding Signages	128	64
Pedestrian Lane	124	62
Pedestrian Crossing	117	58.5
Information Board or Kiosk	115	57.5
Police Outpost	113	56.5
Benches	112	56
Transport Bays	111	55.5
Bike Lane	107	53.5
Public Restrooms	105	52.5
PWD Ramps	104	52
PUV Lanes	95	47.5
Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks	93	46.5
Interpretative Signages and Markers	88	44
Designated food stalls and eateries	71	35.5
Public Parking Spaces	69	34.5
Drinking fountain	56	28
Bollard	43	21.5
Al Fresco/Picnic Tables	41	20.5
Public Art Installations	31	15.5
Water Feature	19	9.5
Children's Playground	14	7
Gazebos and Pavillions	14	7

Table 28. Preference of Landscape Elements in Image 5

The chart and table above showcase the landscape elements preferred by respondents, with respect to their potential integration into the depicted image of old theatres

converted into commercial establishments along Rizal Avenue. The findings indicate the different preferences and priorities of respondents within the area.

Akin to the previous item, CCTV Units emerged as the most prominently desired feature, with 164 individuals, or 82% of respondents, signifying a strong agreement between the need for heightened security measures within the area to enhance the safety of individuals passing through Rizal Avenue, given its reputation as a dark and unsafe thoroughfare. Additionally, landscape elements that garnered a considerable amount of priority include *Trash Receptacles*, *Wayfinding Signages*, *Lamp Posts/Lighting Units*, *Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery*, *Pedestrian Lane*, *Pedestrian Crossing*, and *Information Board or Kiosk* with frequencies of responses spanning from 115 to 135, making up 57.5 to 67.5% of answers. On the contrary, landscape elements with relatively lower frequency scores include *Designated food stalls and eateries*, *Public Parking Spaces*, *Drinking fountain*, *Bollard*, *Al Fresco/Picnic Tables*, *Public Art Installations*, *Water Feature*, *Children's Playground*, and *Gazebos and Pavilions*. A relatively lower priority for their inclusion within the depicted image can be drawn from the obtained frequency in percentage of these landscape elements as the selection of these elements comprised approximately 7% to 35% of the total responses, with scores ranging from 14 to 71.

Image 6: Plaza Miranda Filled with People and Street Vendors

Figure 27. Preferred Landscape Elements for Image 6

IMAGE 6		
LANDSCAPE ELEMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
CCTV Units	174	87
Trash Receptacles	150	75
Trees/Shrubbery	147	73.5
Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks	142	71
Benches	138	69
Wayfinding Signages	138	69
Lamp Posts/Lighting Units	135	67.5
Police Outpost	127	63.5
Designated food stalls and eateries	126	63
Public Restrooms	123	61.5
Information Board or Kiosk	113	56.5
Pedestrian Lane	111	55.5
PWD Ramps	101	50.5
Pedestrian Crossing	101	50.5
Interpretative Signages and Markers	90	45
Bike Lane	90	45
Transport Bays	84	42
PUV Lanes	67	33.5
Public Parking Spaces	64	32
Water Feature	63	31.5
Drinking fountain	62	31
Al Fresco/Picnic Tables	55	27.5
Public Art Installations	52	26
Bollard	51	25.5
Children's Playground	27	13.5
Gazebos and Pavillions	16	8

Table 29. Preference of Landscape Elements in Image 6

The previous chart and table showcase the preferred landscape elements by respondents when asked about their prospective incorporation into the image of Plaza Miranda filled

with people and street vendors. Similar to the previous items, the results indicate the preferences and priorities of the survey participants within the area.

CCTV Units continued to be the repeated most prominently desired landscape element, with 174 individuals, or 87% of respondents, similar to previous responses. This indicates that safety and security remain one of the highest priorities of respondents who selected this landscape element. In addition, the other landscape elements that garnered a considerable amount of priority include *Trash Receptacles*, *Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery*, *Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosk*, *Benches*, *Wayfinding Signages*, *Lamp Posts/Lighting Units*, and *Police Outpost* with frequencies of responses ranges from 127 to 150, constituting nearly 63.5 to 75% of responses.

Consequently, the landscape elements with relatively lower priority due to its low frequency scores include *PUV Lanes*, *Public Parking Spaces* *Water Feature*, *Drinking fountain*, *Al Fresco/Picnic Tables*, *Public Art Installations*, *Bollard*, *Children's Playground*, *Gazebos and Pavilions* as their frequencies ranged from 16 to 67, making up only 8 to 33.5% of answers.

Image 7: Rizal Avenue corner Carriedo Street

Figure 28. Preferred Landscape Elements for Image 7

IMAGE 7		
LANDSCAPE ELEMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
CCTV Units	165	82.5
Pedestrian Lane	145	72.5
Trash Receptacles	140	70
Bike Lane	137	68.5
Lamp Posts/Lighting Units	134	67
Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery	134	67
Wayfinding Signages	133	66.5
Pedestrian Crossing	130	65
Transport Bays	128	64
PUV Lanes	120	60
Police Outpost	118	59
PWD Ramps	107	53.5
Information Board or Kiosk	92	46
Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks	91	45.5
Benches	90	45
Public Restrooms	83	41.5
Public Parking Spaces	72	36
Interpretative Signages and Markers	69	34.5
Designated food stalls and eateries	69	34.5
Bollard	54	27
Al Fresco/Picnic Tables	33	16.5
Public Art Installations	33	16.5
Drinking fountain	32	16
Water Feature	21	10.5
Children's Playground	13	6.5
Gazebos and Pavillions	10	5

Table 30. Preference of Landscape Elements in Image 7

The chart and table above demonstrate the landscape elements preferred by respondents, with respect to their potential integration into the depicted image of Carriedo Street corner Rizal Avenue. The findings reveal the different preferences and priorities of respondents within the area as stipulated by the corresponding frequencies of each landscape element.

Similar to the preceding items, CCTV Units appeared as the most prominently desired feature, with 165 individuals, or 82.5% of respondents, signifying a strong link between the need for heightened security measures within the area to enhance the safety of individuals passing through Rizal Avenue and Carriedo Street, given its reputation as both dark and unsafe thoroughfares. Additionally, landscape elements that garnered a considerable amount of priority include *Pedestrian Lane*, *Trash Receptacles*, *Bike Lane*, *Lamp Posts/Lighting Units*, *Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery*, *Wayfinding Signages*, and *Pedestrian Crossing* with frequencies of responses spanning from 130 to 135, making up 65 to 72.5% of answers.

On the contrary, landscape elements with relatively lower frequency scores include *Interpretative Signages and Markers*, *Designated food stalls and eateries*, *Bollard*, *Al Fresco/Picnic Tables*, *Public Art Installations*, *Drinking fountain*, *Water Feature*, *Children's Playground*, and *Gazebos and Pavillions*. A relatively lower priority for their inclusion within the depicted image can be drawn from the obtained frequency in percentage of these landscape elements as the selection of these elements encompassed approximately 5% to 34.5% of the total responses, with scores spanning from 10 to 69.

Implications of the study

Thematic Analysis of Rizal Avenue's Present Place Character

Rizal Avenue, widely known as Avenida Rizal to many, is revealed to have an important role as a major thoroughfare and as one of Manila's urban transportation corridors. The survey also indicated its significance as a commercial hub containing numerous commercial establishments and landmarks, supporting both formal and informal economies within the vicinity. It is also worth noting that several people have cited the role of Rizal Avenue as an entertainment and cultural district due to the presence of now neglected, albeit architecturally and historically significant buildings. Some of which includes the old movie theatres that can be found along its bustling street, which now has contributed to its negative reputation as a red-light district, as these now defunct cinemas are now used as prostitution dens or places of adult entertainment. In line with this, the responses reveal that the avenue is also a platform where illicit activities and petty crimes have proliferated, where its perpetrators blend among the crowds and its congested streets. In general, negative characteristics can be mostly attributed

to the area, whereas, in several responses, there lies an evident longing for its glorious past as one of Manila's vibrant cinematic and commercial districts in relation to the respondent's personal and past experiences with the site. With these, several multi-faceted themes can be uncovered from the responses within the survey, which are outlined below:

A. Transportation and Infrastructure

The survey responses revealed that Rizal Avenue remains as a vital transportation corridor throughout the years, indicating its significance as a major commuting route. At present, this is due to the presence of the Light Rail Transit (LRT) System, with respondents referencing specific LRT Stations, such as Carriedo, Doroteo Jose, Bambang and Tayuman. Further, several responses shed light on its role as the "gateway to Manila", due to the prominence of bus terminals along the avenue. Based on the responses, numerous buses from nearby provinces tend to traverse through this route, along with public transport or utility vehicles, such as jeepneys, tricycles, and e-trikes. In line with this, the responses also highlight the challenges of heavy traffic congestion, and busy pedestrian and motorist activities along the area – proving its role as a bustling transport corridor.

B. Commercial Establishments and Historical Landmarks

With its past as a former Japanese settlement filled with bazaars that have helped the avenue gain the title of "Little Tokyo" or "Ginza of Manila" during the colonial period, Rizal Avenue remains as a vibrant commercial hub lined with various establishments and landmarks at present. The presence of shopping malls, affordable goods, and a vast myriad of stores with products ranging from food, clothing, furniture, electronics, and others were mentioned prominently among the cohort of responses. In addition, street vendors hailing from its informal economy and its existing vibrant street market culture also contributed to avenue's reputation as a commercial hub. Many historical landmarks, which includes Quiapo Church, Divisoria, Escolta, Manila Grand Opera House, other old movie theatres such as Universal and Ever Theatre, were also a recurring theme among the responses. These landmarks, even though some of them are demolished or do not function in their original state, highlight Rizal Avenue's historical,

cultural, and commercial significance as these landmarks were former destinations within the thoroughfare.

C. Crowd and Congestion

Rizal Avenue is typically characterized by heavy foot and vehicular traffic, and a high volume of people, contributing to its bustling nature. However, many referenced the presence of snatchers, scams, and overall unsafe reputation with the site that go along with the busy landscape character of the avenue. In line with this, the avenue is generally regarded as noisy, chaotic, disorderly, and dangerous, emphasizing the need to address the negative landscape characteristics possessed by the site.

D. Challenges in Conservation Efforts and in Maintaining Desirable Landscape Attributes

In relation to the previous theme, the responses reveal several challenges in preserving the unique landscape character of the site and maintaining positive attributes of the site. Many responses have cited the presence of old structures and buildings, evoking a sense of historical context along the thoroughfare. However, difficulties in conserving these heritage assets persist as a difficult challenge, especially to those who are aware of its significance. Considering this, negative place characteristics, such as the lack of cleanliness and the unpleasant atmosphere due to pollution and dirt, are frequently mentioned. Dimly lit areas and the absence of green spaces are also highlighted, with suggestions made for improved landscape and infrastructure design, which includes the addition of softscape and proper hardscape elements, to enhance the aesthetic and environmental aspects of the avenue.

E. Personal Memories, Associations, and Nostalgia

A number of respondents expressed personal memories, associations, and individual perceptions of Rizal Avenue, maintaining its nature as a memoryscape. Some responses reveal familiarity and a sense of home associated with the avenue, referring to personal experiences, daily commutes, connection between their parents' houses, and the everyday mundaneness of the avenue. This indicates that the landscape character of Rizal Avenue may be defined by the subjective experiences of the respondents with the site, using nostalgia, memories of the past and the historical significance of the site as lenses in which the avenue may be regarded as.

Thematic Analysis of Recto Avenue's Present Place Character

Recto Avenue embodies a diverse range of themes and characteristics based on the responses gathered in the survey. It serves as a bustling commercial hub, housing informal economies and a wide array of commercial establishments, stores, street vendors, and malls. Moreover, the avenue is closely associated with the University Belt and accommodates educational institutions, along with establishments catering to students' needs. However, the area is also plagued by safety concerns due to prevalent criminal activities. Consequently, Recto Avenue is a major transportation hub intersecting LRT train lines, attracting a significant influx of pedestrians. Yet, the avenue is marked by congestion and disorderliness, stemming from heavy traffic and high pedestrian and motorist activity. It boasts historical landmarks and cultural assets, reflecting its vibrant past as an entertainment center. The emergent themes based on the responses are further discussed below:

A. Informal Economy and Commercial Establishments

References to Recto Avenue's role as a platform for informal economies is a recurring theme among the cohort of responses within the survey. Respondents frequently cite the avenue as a bustling commercial hub, embodied by numerous commercial establishments, stores, street vendors, and malls, such as Isetann and Odeon Mall. Specific references to these informal and formal economies include secondhand bookshop stores, school supplies, print and graphics shop, counterfeit documents and products, and other various trading establishments varying from clothing (with the emergence of various ukay-ukay stores along the area), electronics, animals, jewelries, and antique items. Further, the avenue is known for its accessibility to the masses, as it offers affordable and reasonable prices for goods and services.

B. Educational Institutions

The avenue is closely associated with the University Belt, due to the presence of universities and collegiate institutions along the avenue. Frequently mentioned by respondents include Far Eastern University (FEU), University of the East (UE) and other educational institutions. Along with its reputation as a school and academic district, comes various establishments catering to students' academic needs, such as secondhand books, printing services, and school supply stores. On the other hand,

counterfeit academic documents may also be sourced from the avenue, ranging from diplomas, certificates, and even theses or dissertations.

C. Criminal Activities and Safety Concerns

In relation to the previous item, many respondents emphasized the prevalence of illicit and criminal activities within the area, including petty crimes such as theft, pickpocketing, forgery, and the production of fake documents. Some have also cited their own personal experiences, the majority of which are students, with local syndicates and criminals operating within the area. These factors contribute to the negative reputation of Recto Avenue as an unsafe and dangerous place, particularly at night, and most especially for women and children. With this, safety precautions and a sense of caution are common feelings and measures associated with the place due to its criminal nature.

D. Transportation and Connectivity

Similar to Rizal Avenue, Recto Avenue is also recognized as a major transportation hub, popularly known as the intersection of the LRT Line 1 and LRT Line 2 train lines. The avenue is also regarded as the last station of LRT 2 and is known as a popular transit point serving numerous pedestrians throughout the day. The responses also referenced transportation infrastructure, such as the LRT Stations, overpasses, and transportation connections, indicating the significance of the avenue as a transport link and an important transportation corridor within Manila.

E. Congestion and Disorderliness

In relation to the previous item, many respondents characterized Recto Avenue as a crowded and chaotic avenue due to the heavy traffic persisting in the site, and a high volume of pedestrian and motorist activity. Among the cohort of responses, foot and vehicular traffic, the induced pollution and noise by vehicles, and the bustling street life are recurring terms used to describe the place character of the avenue. With this, the overall atmosphere of the place is commonly associated with disorder, messiness, and the challenges posed by the overpopulated and congested nature of the area.

F. Historical and Cultural Assets

Lastly, several respondents have cited the presence of historical landmarks and cultural assets within the site. These include the presence of old theatres and cinemas, such as Roben, Vista Theatre, Hollywood Theatre, Tandem Theatre, Eastern Theatre, Manila Cinema, and Dilson Theatre, reflecting the avenue's historical significance and its role as an entertainment hub in the past. Additionally, references to Bakers Fair and traditional Filipino pastries and delicacies were regarded as common cultural elements associated to the area.

Thematic Analysis of Carriedo Street's Present Place Character

Carriedo Street in Quiapo, Manila, possesses a distinct place character shaped by several key themes. The survey analysis reveals that the street is a vibrant commercial and shopping center, offering a diverse range of products through its bustling markets, shops, and its nickname as the "mini Divisoria." Additionally, Carriedo Street serves as a vital transportation hub, with the LRT Station acting as a landmark and facilitating access to various destinations, including the revered Quiapo Church. The street's cultural and religious significance is evident, as it is closely associated with Quiapo Church and the religious practices surrounding it. Congestion and chaos characterize Carriedo Street, with its crowded atmosphere, street vendors, and occasional disorderly aspects. The street also boasts historical and architectural assets, including landmarks such as Quiapo Church, Carriedo Fountain, and the birthplace of the first ShoeMart store. Lastly, Carriedo Street showcases cultural diversity through the presence of Chinese signages, Muslim vendors, and the fusion of different cultures and cuisines. Understanding these themes is crucial for preserving and enhancing Carriedo Street's unique identity within the urban landscape.

A. Commercial and Shopping Center

Based on the responses in the survey, Carriedo Street is characterized as a bustling commercial area lined with various establishments, including markets, shops, and outlet shops. Respondents mentioned the presence of public markets, vendors, street markets, optical shops, and mini Divisoria, emphasizing the vibrant shopping atmosphere and the availability of a wide range of products.

B. Transportation Hub

The LRT Station located on Carriedo Street serves as a prominent landmark and transportation hub. Many respondents mentioned the LRT station as a point of reference or as a means of access to other locations, such as Quiapo Church and Quiapo in general. The mention of jeepney routes also suggests the significance of Carriedo Street as a transportation hub.

C. Cultural and Religious Significance

Quiapo Church holds cultural and religious importance for the respondents. The area around Carriedo Street is closely associated with Quiapo Church and the practices associated with it. References to churchgoers, Nazareno, prayers, and vendors selling items related to Nazareno indicate the religious significance of the area.

D. Congestion and Chaos

The term "crowded" was frequently used to describe Carriedo Street, suggesting a bustling and lively atmosphere. Respondents mentioned the presence of a large number of people, making it a vibrant and lively street. The presence of street vendors, beggars, and the mention of chaotic or disorderly aspects also contribute to this theme.

E. Historical and Architectural Assets

Carriedo Street is characterized by the presence of old buildings and historical elements. Respondents mentioned the street's association with historical landmarks such as Quiapo Church, Carriedo Fountain, and the birthplace of the first ShoeMart store. These references highlight the historical and architectural significance of the street.

F. Cultural Diversity

The mention of Chinese signages, Chinese delicacies, and Muslim vendors highlights the cultural diversity and multicultural nature of Carriedo Street. It serves as a hub for various communities, where different cultures, cuisines, and businesses intersect.

Thematic Analysis of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip's Heritage

Three prominent themes emerge when describing heritage: legacy, culture, and history. These themes hold particular relevance when considering Rizal Avenue, Carriedo Street, and Recto Avenue in relation to heritage preservation. These terms are legacy, culture and history. Which operational definitions are discussed below:

1. Legacy — This term highlights the idea of heritage as something passed down from previous generations. It signifies the importance of preserving and maintaining cultural traditions, customs, and historical artifacts.
2. Culture — Culture is frequently mentioned as a key aspect of heritage. It encompasses the customs, traditions, beliefs, and practices that are inherited and cherished by a community or society.
3. History — History is another significant term associated with heritage. It emphasizes the historical significance of inherited objects, landmarks, and narratives that contribute to a collective identity and understanding of the past.

According to the responses of the participants in relation to Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, these elements of heritage interplay with the landscape character of the site. Firstly, the notion of legacy resonates strongly in the context of these streets. Rizal Avenue, named after the national hero Jose Rizal, carries a sense of historical significance and the enduring impact of his ideals. It serves as a reminder of the legacy left by Rizal and his contributions to the nation's identity and struggle for independence. Carriedo Street, known for its vibrant market and bustling trade, represents a legacy of commerce and entrepreneurship, passed down through generations. Recto Avenue, on the other hand, bears witness to a legacy of academic excellence and intellectual discourse, being home to various educational institutions and bookstores.

Secondly, culture is intricately intertwined with the heritage of these streets. Rizal Avenue, Carriedo Street, and Recto Avenue serve as cultural hubs, where diverse traditions, practices, and beliefs converge. They reflect the rich tapestry of Filipino culture, evident in the variety of shops, food establishments, and landmarks that line these streets. These cultural expressions contribute to the sense of place and identity for both locals and visitors, making them significant sites of cultural heritage.

Lastly, history plays a pivotal role in understanding and preserving the heritage of these streets. Rizal Avenue, with its historical references to Jose Rizal, embodies the historical narrative of the nation and serves as a reminder of the struggles and sacrifices made in the pursuit of

freedom. Carriedo Street's history as a bustling market reflects the evolving economic landscape of the country and the enduring spirit of trade. Similarly, Recto Avenue's historical connection to education and academia evokes a sense of intellectual heritage and the pursuit of knowledge.

Landscape Preference and Improvement

The findings from the Landscape Preference and Improvement shed light on the priorities expressed by respondents regarding the enhancement of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. The survey participants consistently identified the presence of CCTV Units as the top priority within the study site, recognizing the crucial need for enhanced surveillance and security measures in the area. This consensus emphasizes the community's concern for safety and the desire for a secure environment within the urban landscape.

Furthermore, Lamp Posts and Police Outposts emerged as two of the most highly desired landscape elements, indicating the respondents' shared belief in the importance of well-lit spaces and visible security presence. These elements contribute to creating a sense of safety and well-being for individuals traversing the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, aligning with the community's aspirations for a secure urban environment.

In addition to the aforementioned landscape elements, the respondents expressed the need for other key features to improve the study site. Trash receptacles were deemed essential, reflecting the community's emphasis on cleanliness and the mitigation of pollution within the urban landscape. The inclusion of softscape materials, such as trees, shrubbery, and greenery, was also highly valued, indicating a desire to integrate natural elements that enhance the aesthetic appeal and environmental quality of the area. Moreover, the provision of public restrooms was recognized as a priority, catering to the needs of the population and improving the overall convenience and comfort of visitors to the site. Respondents also emphasized the importance of addressing disorderliness and chaos within the area. Wayfinding signage and information boards or kiosks were identified as necessary landscape elements to guide users and pedestrians, providing them with essential information about the physical context of the site. This highlights the community's desire for a more organized and user-friendly environment.

Accessibility was another significant aspect that emerged from the respondents' preferences. The inclusion of PWD Ramps and pedestrian lanes was strongly emphasized, reflecting the community's commitment to inclusivity and the provision of adequate facilities for individuals with disabilities. Furthermore, the integration of transportation bays and bike lanes was suggested to support multi-modal transportation options and provide convenient commuter facilities within the study site.

These findings hold significant implications for urban planners, designers, and decision-makers involved in the improvement of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. Understanding the landscape elements preferred by the community enables stakeholders to allocate resources effectively and prioritize interventions that align with the needs and desires of the population. By incorporating the identified priorities, urban planners can create a more secure, accessible, aesthetically pleasing, and user-friendly urban environment that enhances the overall quality of life for those utilizing the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

Conclusion

This study investigated the present landscape character of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip through the landscape perception survey and evidence synthesis procedure. Moreover, it also determined the preferences of landscape elements that can be incorporated into 7 sites within the study area. The results reveal that the Rizal Avenue, Recto Avenue, and Carriedo Street are all significant thoroughfares in Manila, Philippines, each with its own distinct characteristics and contributions to the urban landscape.

In synthesizing the information gathered regarding Rizal Avenue, Recto Avenue, and Carriedo Street, several common themes emerge that shed light on the significance of these thoroughfares within the urban landscape of Manila. Firstly, historical significance is evident as these streets are associated with landmarks and figures of historical importance, such as Rizal Avenue's association with the national hero Jose Rizal and Recto Avenue's namesake, Claro M. Recto, a prominent nationalist statesman. The inclusion of cultural and religious landmarks, such as Quiapo Church along Carriedo Street, further reinforces the historical and cultural value attributed to these streets. Secondly, the commercial vitality of these streets is notable, with Rizal Avenue and Recto Avenue serving as bustling commercial centers characterized by a diverse range of shops, including department stores, bookstores, and

electronics retailers. Carriedo Street, on the other hand, is renowned for its vibrant street markets, vendors, and shopping centers, which attract visitors and shoppers alike. Additionally, these streets function as important transportation hubs within Manila, with the presence of Light Rail Transit (LRT) stations along Rizal Avenue, Recto Avenue, and Carriedo Street, facilitating commuter accessibility and connectivity within the city.

The cultural and ethnic diversity of these streets is evident through the presence of diverse communities and businesses. Respondents highlighted the presence of Chinese signages and delicacies along Carriedo Street, as well as the multicultural fabric reflected in the communities surrounding Rizal Avenue and Recto Avenue. This cultural diversity contributes to the vibrancy and cultural tapestry of these streets. Moreover, the streetscapes of Rizal Avenue, Recto Avenue, and Carriedo Street are characterized by vibrant street life. Descriptions of crowded spaces, bustling street vendors, and markets highlight the energy and liveliness that permeate these areas, creating a distinct urban atmosphere. Lastly, the architectural highlights found along these streets, such as old buildings, landmarks, and monuments, further enhance their appeal and contribute to their heritage value. These architectural elements serve as reminders of the historical and cultural significance associated with these streets, preserving the city's architectural heritage.

On the other hand, the findings of the Landscape Preference and Improvement study provide valuable insights into the priorities expressed by respondents regarding the enhancement of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. The community's strong emphasis on safety is evident through the overwhelming consensus on the need for CCTV Units, lamp posts, and police outposts. These landscape elements contribute to creating a secure environment and instilling a sense of safety among users of the study site. The inclusion of trash receptacles, softscape materials, public restrooms, wayfinding signage, and information boards addresses the community's concerns about cleanliness, aesthetics, organization, and convenience within the area. Additionally, the emphasis on accessibility through the provision of PWD ramps, pedestrian lanes, transportation bays, and bike lanes reflects the community's commitment to inclusivity and sustainable transportation options. These findings provide crucial guidance for urban planners and decision-makers in designing and implementing interventions that align with the community's aspirations, ultimately contributing to the creation of a safer, more accessible, and user-friendly urban environment in the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

Memoryscapes in Recto-spection:
Visualizing Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoryscapes
through immersive mobile technologies and digital heritage interpretation

In summary, the findings emphasize the multifaceted significance of Rizal Avenue, Recto Avenue, and Carriedo Street within the urban landscape of Manila. These streets serve as dynamic hubs of historical, commercial, transportation, and cultural activity, embodying the diverse and evolving nature of the city. The cultural tapestry, historical landmarks, commercial vitality, transportation accessibility, vibrant street life, and architectural heritage found along these streets collectively contribute to the rich and layered urban fabric of Manila.

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